

Grant Agreement No: 951754

FCCIS

Future Circular Collider Innovation Study

Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Framework Programme, Research and Innovation Action

DELIVERABLE REPORT

PLAN FOR RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE SOCIO- ECONOMIC IMPACT ANALYSIS

Document identifier:	FCCIS-P1-WP4-D12 10.5281/zenodo.5725806
Due date:	End of Month 10 (September 2021)
Date:	07/09/2021
Work package/unit:	WP4 Impact and Sustainability
Organisation:	CSIL
Version:	V1.0
Status:	RELEASED
Keywords:	FCC, socio-economic impacts, costs, benefits, technological spillover, scientific outputs, visitors, educational benefits, value of discovery

Abstract:

A publicly available overview and guideline for the analysis of the socio-economic impact analysis of the FCC-ee research infrastructure. The plan compiles impact pathways and associated key performance indicators, a description of the quantitative analysis method for each impact pathway and the preliminary set of input parameters for this project.

Copyright notice:

Copyright © FCCIS Consortium, 2020

For more information on FCCIS, its partners and contributors please see <https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/FCC/FCCIS>.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 951754.

Delivery Slip

	Name	Organisation	Date
Authored by	Johannes Gutleber	CERN	27/04/2020
Authored by	Emanuela Sirtori	CSIL	26/05/2020
Authored by	Francesco Giffoni, Francesca Guadagno, Gelsomina Catalano	CSIL	22/07/2021
Reviewed by	Emanuela Sirtori	CSIL	26/07/2021
Reviewed by	Christian Caron	SPRINGER	28/07/2021
Reviewed by	Gabriele Piazza	LSE	29/07/2021
Reviewed by	Leslie Alix	LAPP	29/07/2021
Reviewed by	Francesco Giffoni, Francesca Guadagno, Gelsomina Catalano, Emanuela Sirtori	CSIL	30/07/2021
Edited by	Anna Yaneva	CERN	04/08/2021
Edited by	Johannes Gutleber	CERN	11/08/2021 to 07/09/2021 23/09/2021
Approved by	Michael Benedikt	CERN	24/11/2021

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.	INTRODUCTION	4
1.1.	BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES.....	4
1.2.	RELATION WITH OTHER STUDY'S TASKS.....	6
1.3.	STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT.....	6
2.	SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT MODEL	7
2.1.	IMPACT PATHWAY METHODOLOGY.....	7
2.2.	IMPACT PATHWAYS.....	9
3.	SCOPE AND KEY PARAMETERS	11
3.1.	OPTION ANALYSIS AND PROJECT IDENTIFICATION.....	11
3.2.	PROJECT TIME HORIZON AND SCHEDULE.....	11
3.3.	PROJECT PARTICIPANTS.....	12
3.4.	PROJECT COSTS.....	15
3.4.1.	<i>Capital expenditures</i>	15
3.4.2.	<i>Operating expenditures</i>	16
3.5.	SOCIAL DISCOUNT RATE (SDR).....	17
3.5.1.	<i>Context and rationale</i>	17
3.5.2.	<i>Interpretation of the SDR</i>	17
3.5.3.	<i>Project SDR value</i>	17
3.6.	THE COUNTERFACTUAL SCENARIO.....	20
3.6.1.	<i>Context, definition and rationale</i>	20
3.6.2.	<i>Counterfactual scenario of the FCC-ee project</i>	21
4.	ASSUMPTIONS, DATA & METHODS FOR THE MODEL	22
4.1.	IMPACT PATHWAY 1: THE VALUE OF SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTS FOR THE SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY.....	22
4.1.1.	<i>Definition of the benefit</i>	22
4.1.2.	<i>Assumptions</i>	22
4.2.	IMPACT PATHWAY 2: EDUCATION AND TRAINING.....	26
4.2.1.	<i>Definition of the benefit</i>	26
4.2.2.	<i>Assumptions</i>	26
4.3.	IMPACT PATHWAY 3: INDUSTRIAL SPILLOVERS.....	30
4.3.1.	<i>Definition of the benefit</i>	30
4.3.2.	<i>Assumptions</i>	30
4.4.	IMPACT PATHWAY 4: DATA, INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES.....	36
4.4.1.	<i>Definition of the benefit</i>	36
4.4.2.	<i>Assumptions</i>	36
4.5.	IMPACT PATHWAY 5: CULTURAL BENEFITS.....	38
4.5.1.	<i>Definition of the benefit</i>	38
4.5.2.	<i>Assumptions</i>	38
4.6.	IMPACT PATHWAY 6: THE PUBLIC GOOD VALUE OF KNOWLEDGE.....	46
4.6.1.	<i>Definition of the benefit</i>	46
4.6.2.	<i>Assumptions</i>	47
5.	REGIONAL AND TERRITORIAL BENEFITS	53
5.1.	TERRITORIAL BENEFITS OF PROCUREMENT.....	53
5.2.	TERRITORIAL BENEFITS IN THE HOST-STATES.....	54
6.	REFERENCES	58
7.	ANNEXES	64
7.1.	FCC-EE PROJECT PARTICIPANTS: TABLES.....	64
7.2.	REVIEW OF SOCIAL DISCOUNT RATES ADOPTED WORLDWIDE.....	67
7.3.	ESTIMATED SALARY FUNCTIONS BY PROFESSIONAL SECTOR.....	68
7.4.	ESTIMATED DURATION OF ACTIVE WORKING LIFE.....	72
7.5.	WILLINGNESS-TO-PAY VALUES FOR NON-USERS OF THE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE.....	78

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

This document has been prepared in the framework of **Work Package 4 - Impact & sustainability** - whose objective is to develop the financial roadmap of the infrastructure project, including the cost estimates, the financing plan, and the analysis of socio-economic impacts.

The specific objective of this report is to lay down the **methods and input parameters for a quantitative socio-economic impact analysis of the lepton collider-based research infrastructure FCC-ee**.

This document describes the overall methodological framework adopted for the estimates of the project's future socio-economic benefits, including the definition of the impact pathways, the input parameters and their values and fundamental assumptions which will be used to perform the analysis, data sources and methods for data collection and methods of analysis.

The report should be understood as a **“living document”**: the framework will be further fine-tuned and specified in the course of the project. Updates will be included in future versions of this document. The methodology will be used to quantify and evaluate the different socio-economic impacts expected to be generated during the FCC-ee project lifetime.

The methodology presented in this report **builds on the results of previous works** carried out by CSIL and CERN for the socio-economic evaluation of the LHC/HL-LHC programme. It also leverages the findings from the H2020 RIPATHS project. Box 1 below provides more details on relevant existing works used in this project.

Box 1. Main sources of information for the socio-economic impact assessment model

Cost-Benefit Analysis in the Research, Development and Innovation Sector (funded by the EIB University Research Sponsorship programme, 2013-2016, carried out by CSIL and University of Milan). The project developed a model for assessing the socio-economic impacts of Big Science, including impacts on knowledge production, human capital, technological learning, cultural effects and good public value. The model was tested on an example for a fundamental scientific research infrastructure, the CERN LHC, and an example of applied research infrastructure, the National Centre for Oncological Treatment (CNAO) in Pavia. The evaluation framework is described in Florio and Sirtori (2016), while the evaluation of LHC and CNAO are reported respectively by Florio, Forte and Sirtori (2016) and Battistoni et al. (2016).

RIPATHS - Charting Impact Pathways of Investment in Research Infrastructure (Horizon2020 project agreement N° 777563, 2018-2020, consortium led by EFIS and including CSIL; ESF, Fraunhofer ISI, CERN, Elixir, Alba and Desy). The project developed a model to describe the pathways of materialisation of the socio-economic impacts of research infrastructures and define a set of indicators and appropriate methodologies to assess them. The framework was developed in a modular manner, adapting it to a broad range of scientific domains and types of infrastructures. It was tested with case studies involving CERN, Alba, Elixir, and Desy. The project's outputs can be consulted at <https://ri-paths.eu/deliverable/>. The web-based modular impact assessment model is available at <https://ri-paths.eu/ri-pahts-ia-model/>.

Ex-ante impact assessment of the HL-LHC infrastructures (CERN, 2015-2019, carried out by University of Milan in collaboration with CSIL and Roma 3 University). The project consisted in evaluating the costs and socio-economic benefits to the scientific community, students and researchers, enterprises, and the general population of the upgrade of the LHC into the High-Luminosity LHC. The result also mentioned in the FCC Conceptual Design Report published by Springer at <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1140/epjst/e2019-900087-0> can be downloaded from the CERN Document Server (CDS) at <http://cds.cern.ch/record/2319300>.

Socio-economic impact at CERN: Social networks and onsite CERN visitors (master thesis by Irene Crespo Garrido, February 2020). This research investigated the benefits generated for on-site and virtual visitors for CERN activities for the public (e.g. on site tours and exhibitions, LHC's presence on YouTube, Facebook, Twitter and other virtual channels). Details can be found at <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2711506>.

Guidelines for the collection of harmonized cost data for Research Infrastructures (technical assistance to the University of Milan, Dept. Physics, for the H2020 StR-ESFRI project (Support to Reinforce the European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures, 2018-2019). CSIL developed a document (StR-ESFRI, 2019) with technical solutions for the collection of harmonized data on the cost related to the life cycle of the research infrastructures of the ESFRI Roadmap. These guidelines provide a conceptual and methodological tool for cost estimation of Research Infrastructures, and the final report of this study illustrates general principles and suggests technical solutions when data seem not immediately available or difficult to estimate. It also considers the specificities of different typologies of research infrastructures, which are active in different research domains and adopt different accounting systems.

1.2. RELATION WITH OTHER STUDY'S TASKS

As mentioned above, this report will guide the work to be carried out under Task 4.3 of the project, consisting of the ex-ante socio-economic impact assessment of the lepton collider-based research infrastructure. However, it is expected to be synergic and complementary with other tasks carried out in the framework of the FCCIS project, specifically:

- **WP4, task 4.4: Regional and territorial benefit potential identification.** The socio-economic impact analysis model will provide data and estimates to guide the development of local and regional impact opportunities in the two host-states France and Switzerland. This requires establishing interfaces with regional industrial partners, stakeholders of different interest groups and host-state notified bodies and can significantly help improving the social acceptability of the project.
- **WP4, tasks 4.2 and 4.5:** These tasks involve the **estimation of costs** and the spending profile of the FCC-ee project. The estimation of benefits occurs in parallel with the cost estimates (Task 4.2). They will jointly contribute to the **implementation, financing and in-kind contribution strategy** for the project (Task 4.5). Both costs and benefits have to be taken into account to develop a proper strategy for the long-term sustainability of the project.
- **WP3:** The outputs of the **territorial integration activities** (the optimisation of the layout and placement of the FCC, resource needs, risks, the economic potential of the reuse of excavated materials) will be taken into account in the socio-economic impact model, as they may feed into the assessment of specific benefits (e.g. industrial spillovers of firms involved in the excavation and civil engineering works) and particular parameters of the probabilistic risk model.
- **WP5:** The results of Task 4.3 will be used to plan and produce **communication and dissemination materials**. They can also be taken into account in the activities to engage scientists, stakeholders, or lay people in the scientific activities.

1.3. STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

After this introductory section explaining the background and objectives of the deliverable, the report is structured as follows:

- Chapter 2 outlines the overall approach adopted in the socio-economic impact analysis model;
- Chapter 3 presents the project scope, the key parameters and assumptions underpinning the analysis, namely: the time horizon, the social discount rate and the counterfactual scenario. Some data on the future project participants and cost items are also presented, with the aim of providing a complete set of background information about the project;
- Chapter 4 discusses the assumptions, data and methods for the model implementation, specifically for the estimation of the different impact pathways;
- Chapter 5 provides ideas for the estimation of the territorial and regional benefits of FCC-ee which complement the impact pathway analysis described in Chapter 4.

The Annexes provide complementary information and data.

2. SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT MODEL

2.1. IMPACT PATHWAY METHODOLOGY

Policy makers expect research infrastructures to be essential components of technological and scientific progress (EC, 2010; ESFRI, 2010; Technopolis, 2011; ESF, 2013). Traditionally, the appraisal process of research infrastructure projects relied on the scientific community's own internal mechanisms and the policy context. Typically, these mechanisms involve a community-based process that assesses the 'science case', sometimes complemented by a 'business case' or considerations related to the socio-economic impacts (Feller, 2013). This approach is today no longer the only decision basis for new investments in scientific research infrastructure projects. For instance, it does not account for planning a new research infrastructure with the development of socio-economic effects from the beginning on. For this reason, specific evaluation tools and methods are being developed by associations of national and international funding bodies.

Recently, a **more strategic approach to research infrastructure investments has been promoted at international level**, with the development of roadmaps to prioritise research infrastructures (ESFRI, 2008; OECD, 2008; Research Council UK, 2010). Such roadmaps assess research infrastructures according to a set of qualitative and quantitative criteria ranging from scientific and technological excellence to socio-economic impact indicators, governance and financial aspects. In some cases, also risk factors are considered.

However, **no consensus exists today on a single evaluation model**; instead, a variety of different approaches are used in different countries and economic regions (Pancotti, *et al.*, 2014, Pozzo, *et al* 2019, Vignetti, S 2021, Catalano, G. *et al.* 2021). Various conceptual frameworks have been proposed in parallel by different teams. These frames have however in common to consider a range of observable direct and indirect effects and longer-term impacts and reflect different information needs of funding institutions, policy and decision-makers and science managers. A heterogeneous set of methods is applied to capture these effects (European Commission, 2020, Giffoni and Vignetti 2019).

This lack of consensus hinders the possibility to systematically compare the impacts of different projects that may compete for scarce funding, and to compare ex-ante, on-going, and ex-post evaluations, as suggested by the best international practice for project appraisals of major infrastructures.

Against the demand for credible and recognised methodologies to assess research infrastructures, the RIPATH project, funded by the Horizon 2020 programme (see Box 1 above), aimed at developing a conceptual model describing the socio-economic impacts of RIs and their related financial investments, applying to a wide range of infrastructures and scientific fields (Griniece, E. *et al* 2020). The model identifies and describes the different pathways involved in the generation of socio-economic impacts and defines a set of indicators and methodologies to assess them. These **pathways are defined as the (non-linear) sequence of steps linking a research infrastructure to its direct and tangible outputs, the socio-economic outcomes attributed to that infrastructure, up to more indirect, wider and not necessarily quantifiable impacts**. The RIPATH project lists the most relevant indicators used to track the future outputs, outcomes and impacts of a research infrastructure, as well as methodologies for impact measurement, but it also recommends the use of various qualitative analyses (narratives, case studies, etc.) to report on the most intangible impacts.

Following the approach defined by the RIPATH project and the most recent practice of economic quantification of impacts of research infrastructures,¹ the impact analysis model for the FCC-ee rests on the following pillars:

- A **long-term perspective** is taken, covering the entire lifetime of the FCC-ee;
- The **"impact pathway logic"** is adopted to identify the benefits, from the immediate outputs to short-term, long-term outcomes and, ultimately wider impacts;
- The values of the most relevant and measurable impacts are quantified into **monetary terms**;
- Only impacts that can be **causally attributed** to the FCC-ee project are considered for a quantitative estimation;

¹ Evidenced by several publications on this topic in peer-reviewed journals (see list of references in Chapter 6).

- A **Social Discount Rate (SDR)**, estimated following the standard practice in economics, is adopted to estimate the present value of future benefits and to ensure comparability of benefits that occur at different times;
- A **probabilistic model** based on historical data and expert consensus agreement is built to forecast the probability of occurrence of the impacts: this means that a Monte Carlo simulation model will be used to estimate the probability distribution function of the impacts and to identify the factors that critically affect the impacts;
- **Prudence and transparency** are key requirements for the entire model development.

The socio-economic impacts model described in this document will focus on the *direct and quantifiable* impacts of the FCC-ee project. In doing this, the net gain for the society expressed in monetary terms may appear small when compared to the capital and operation expenditure of the project, as it does not account for the intangible impacts (e.g. scientific knowledge gain², impacts related to science diplomacy, ethics and trust in science, impacts on policies, etc.) and the impacts of those scientific discoveries that cannot be predicted and therefore remain unknown for a long time. This does not mean that the value of a new research infrastructure is not justified. On the contrary, knowing that the project will generate *at least* the estimated measurable wealth for society is crucial to **help designing the research infrastructure with long-term sustainability in mind**.

The ESFRI Working Group on the long-term sustainability of research infrastructure stresses the **importance of scientific excellence and outstanding quality services as conditions *since qua non*** for sustainability throughout the entire research infrastructure lifecycle. Incorporating the economic and social value of research infrastructures into science-policy-society dialogue is one of the main recommendations set by the working group (ESFRI, 2017). In line with this recommendation, **long term sustainability of a new mission-oriented research infrastructure can be achieved by ensuring that public spending creates at least some measurable wealth for as many members of society as possible**. In this case, the results of the socio-economic impact analysis can inform decisions about the design and operation of FCC-ee, helping to maximise the number of potential users/beneficiaries, the value they may get out of the infrastructure and, ultimately, social acceptability for the project.

² Beyond what can be measured through publications and other immediate scientific products.

2.2. IMPACT PATHWAYS

In line with the standard practice of impact assessment applied to research infrastructures and other major investment projects (Griniece, E. et al. 2020, Florio, Forte, and Sirtori, E. 2016, European Commission 2014), the identification of the impact areas of a project requires first the **identification of the project’s potential beneficiaries**, i.e. the groups of the population that would directly benefit from the project. For each group, corresponding impact areas can be identified. In turn, for each impact area, a pathway can be traced to describe the way in which the FCC-ee project generates impacts first on its direct users and next to further members of the society.

The impact pathways considered for the FCC-ee and the respective beneficiaries are illustrated in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. The FCC-ee socio-economic impact model: conceptual framework

1. **Impact Pathway IP.1 - SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTS** describes the flows of knowledge generated by scientists working at the collider and its experiments. This knowledge is captured in a wide range of scientific products ranging from **scientific publications over conference and workshop participation and presentations, books and working papers**. Scientific products can be cited and eventually become part of a new body of knowledge that can also find recognition or interest beyond the High-Energy Physics (HEP) community. Ultimately, newly generated scientific knowledge may further spread out into other impact areas, such as industrial spillovers (in the form of increased competitiveness, an enlarged customer base, gain of reputation, improved technologies) and it may be used to help solving grand societal challenges. This pathway may be therefore connected to IP.3 (Industrial Spillovers) and IP.6 (Public Good Value).
2. **Impact Pathway IP.2 – EDUCATION AND TRAINING** describes the **FCC-ee’s contribution in the transmission of knowledge and know-how, skills development and capacity which may occur to early-career researchers through actively participating in the research project** during the design, construction, commissioning and operation phases. This study considers apprentices, trainees, technical students, doctoral students, post-doctoral researchers, associated members of personnel up to a cut-off age. The benefit is likely to materialise in terms of lifetime career development improvements after the experience in the research programme.
3. **Impact Pathway IP.3 – INDUSTRIAL SPILLOVERS** explores the impacts that the programme is expected to generate on companies that participate in the design, construction and operation of this new research infrastructure by means of technological and/or knowledge spillovers. These spillovers are likely to materialise through two different (but not necessarily distinct) pathways: first, **via the procurement activity** during which suppliers interact with scientists and engineers. When supplier companies work closely with the research infrastructure to develop and improve technologies there is

an exchange of ideas and knowledge between parties, which feeds the creation or improvements of new processes, products and services that supplier companies can also exploit in other markets, beyond high energy physics or for other scientific research projects, making them eventually cheaper and more performing.

4. **Impact Pathway IP.4 – ICT and DATA SPILLOVERS** describes how the programme can generate impacts thanks to the development of **free and open-source software and the making available of open data**. Therefore, this pathway ramifies into many possible branches depending on the conditions under which the ICT software/data are delivered (open access, public, restricted), the extent of their usage and the type of organization outside CERN using such ICT tools (firms, researchers in university, other institutions, etc.). This pathway may be therefore connected to IP.1 and IP.3.
5. **Impact Pathway IP.5 - CULTURAL EFFECTS** traces the impacts of activities that engage a wide audience. These activities can be directly related to the scientific research activities, can relate to the technologies used for this science and can relate to the activities to design and operate the frontier particle accelerators and experiments. Direct beneficiaries are both **in-person and online (virtual) visitors**. The ultimate impact is in terms of awareness-raising, increased interest and understanding of any member of the society towards science. For this reason, it is also linked with IP.6.
6. **Impact Pathway IP.6 - PUBLIC GOOD VALUE**. FCC-ee will produce knowledge about the nature and the functioning of the universe, which are considered a ‘public good’. The provision of such public good is financed by the taxpayers in those countries that contribute to the design, construction and operation; therefore, taxpayers are ultimately the funders of the FCC. Even if there may be no immediate application or use of the fundamental scientific knowledge produced for laypersons, previous studies have shown that citizens are willing to financially support that research for the interest and for the conviction that there is utility for humankind in this activity. The public good value pathway estimates the **value that individual persons attribute to the mere existence of the FCC-ee project, because of the satisfaction and curiosity about the research activity carried out there and its potential contribution to understanding the inner workings of the Universe**. Beneficiaries are people who are expected to use the services that the FCC infrastructure provides, i.e. who may not even visit the infrastructure (IP.5), or understand the content of the scientific knowledge produced by scientists (IP.1), or make no use of the data made publicly available (IP.4) or technologies developed by the industry (IP.3), etc. Even so, this IP is indirectly connected with all the other IPs considered.

3. SCOPE AND KEY PARAMETERS

3.1. OPTION ANALYSIS AND PROJECT IDENTIFICATION

Over the past ten years, the particle physics community has been discussing and considering different post High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) scenarios, all aiming at further exploring the Higgs mechanism and providing knowledge advancement in fundamental physics. These scenarios are quite different in terms of technical features (e.g., performance, particle accelerator type and size, number of experiments, etc.), construction and operation costs, timelines for carrying out the physics programmes, as well as interaction with the existing Large-Hadron Collider. A **strategic options analysis has been implemented as a first step of the socio-economic impact analysis**, as recommended by the European Commission (2014). The rationale for this analysis comes from the awareness that any investment entails the decision of not undertaking another option. Therefore, in order to properly assess the technical, economic and environmental suitability of an investment, an adequate range of options have been compared as a starting point.

The impact analysis model will consider the impacts expected to be generated by the FCC-ee project only. The model will not compare the impacts of FCC-ee with the possible impacts of alternative project scenarios since each of them would require dedicated studies. However, to present the *net* direct impacts of the project, this analysis will compare the estimated impacts of the FCC-ee with a “without-the-project scenario” (counterfactual scenario), which is discussed in Section 3.6.

3.2. PROJECT TIME HORIZON AND SCHEDULE

Figure 2 outlines the project schedule considered for the socio-economic study. It ranges from the design to the end of the operation phase for the particle collider and two experiments. The time plan foresees the first capital expenditures in 2028. After some years for design and construction, the infrastructure and experiments are expected to begin operation by 2041 with a commissioning period. The operation phase will continue until 2055, but data analysis will occur for a few years more. In total, **the time horizon of the FCC-ee covers 30 years, from 2028 to 2057**. This schedule should be considered as indicative as it is certainly subject to updates depending on the project context and external constraints.

Figure 2. FCC-ee schedule considered for the socio-economic impact analysis

3.3. PROJECT PARTICIPANTS

The figures below outline the estimated number of project participants by category. For the project participants **two segments** are considered: firstly, **members of the experiment collaborations** with persons at CERN for limited time periods. Secondly, **persons participating in the particle collider and technical infrastructure projects** with personnel predominantly present at CERN and with collaborating institutes world-wide.

The presented number of persons who would be active in the FCC-ee science programme is **based on a conservative scaling estimate of the LHC experiments** (particularly CMS, which has a size that is similar to the envisaged FCC-ee experiments) **and on the historical human resource databases of CERN for the accelerator and technology-related departments** between 1993 and 2020.

Considering that departments at CERN were re-structured various times and considering that the experiment collaborations were not keeping detailed accounts about different classes of persons engaged in the programme throughout the entire period, the split between different person classes had to be based on estimates. For instance, the exact number of doctoral students is known since about 2005, but the exact number of scientists engaged worldwide is only tracked since 2016. Similar situations are true for the accounting of technicians and undergraduate students.

Figure 3 outlines the estimated number of participants in **two FCC-ee experiment projects** by splitting them into the following categories: scientists, doctoral and post-doctoral students, engineers, undergraduate students, technicians and administration. **For the period 2028 to 2057, 128 240 people are foreseen to be actively involved in the two FCC-ee experiment collaborations** (i.e. 64 240 for each experiment collaboration). Annex 7.1 reports more detailed numbers.

Figure 3. Personnel evolution estimate of one typical FCC-ee experiment collaboration

In addition to the people involved in the experiment collaborations, it is estimated that **87 820 people will be involved in the particle accelerator and technical infrastructure projects** (see Figure 4 and Annex 7.1). Most of these persons will work at the project premises.

Figure 4. Estimated personnel evolution at the FCC-ee particle accelerator and technical infrastructure.

Note: For the socio-economic impact analysis, the observation period ends two years after the last data taking. This lead-out phase is dedicated to continuing the analysis of data and therefore significant amounts of personnel participating in the particle physics experiments remain engaged.

Figure 5 depicts the sum of the two project segments (collaborative experiments, particle accelerator and technical infrastructures). Considering the expected **total person engagement between 2028 and 2057, 216 300 people will be involved in the FCC-ee scientific programme** with the following distribution:

- Scientists, n = 106 500 (49%)
- Doctoral and post-doctoral students, n = 31 720 (15%)
- Engineers, n =13 710 (6%)
- Undergraduate students, n = 16 450 (8%)
- Technicians, Administration, n = 47 920 (22%).

The personnel estimates do not consider persons participating in civil engineering construction activities and persons who are directly employed by contractors. Those are under the responsibility of those companies and bidder groups.

Figure 5. Estimated total number of people involved in the FCC-ee scientific programme (experiments, accelerators and infrastructure) at CERN and in the worldwide collaborations.

Note: The figure includes the number of people involved in two experiments, the particle accelerator and technical infrastructure projects. This conservative estimate considers that, at the start of construction, in total about 2 000 persons are active in the worldwide collaboration with about 1 500 persons at CERN. This figure does not include people who are engaged in civil construction works. As the project moves into the operation phase, the number of participants in the experiment projects will steadily increase to about 10 000 persons and the number of persons active in the particle accelerator and technology sectors will reach about 4 000 persons. Most scientists participating in the research activities are not assumed to be permanently at CERN and they will mainly be employed by their home institutes. This figure includes all contracted labour. About 2 000 persons would be active under the direct responsibility of CERN, representing about 80% of the persons engaged by CERN today. The same share applies to the LHC and HL-LHC projects.

3.4. PROJECT COSTS

3.4.1. Capital expenditures

The FCC-ee project is conceived as a design-to-cost project, with a total investment around 10 billion CHF. Investments will be made gradually after decision to construct from ca. 2028 to 2035. Some reinvestments will be made during the FCC operations.

Table 1 below shows the different investment cost items and their foreseen years of occurrence. The quantification of the impacts will be made in Swiss francs (CHF).

Table 1. Investment cost items of FCC-ee

System	Domain	Start year of investment	Years of investment	Year of completion
Main ring magnet system	Accelerator	2033	6	2039
Main ring vacuum system	Accelerator	2033	6	2039
Main ring power converters and cabling	Accelerator	2033	5	2038
Main ring beam transfer systems	Accelerator	2033	6	2039
Main ring beam diagnostics	Accelerator	2033	6	2039
Other main ring (controls, protection)	Accelerator	2033	6	2039
Injector magnet system	Accelerator	2032	5	2037
Injector vacuum system	Accelerator	2032	5	2037
Injector power converts & cabling	Accelerator	2032	5	2037
Injector beam transfer systems	Accelerator	2032	5	2037
Injector beam diagnostics	Accelerator	2032	5	2037
Other injector (controls, protection)	Accelerator	2032	5	2037
Main and top-up ring RF system (Z)	Accelerator	2035	4	2039
Main and top-up ring RF system (W)	Accelerator	2042	2	2044
Main and top-up ring RF system (H)	Accelerator	2041	6	2047
Main and top-up ring RF system (ttbar)	Accelerator	2041	8	2049
Cryogenics	Accelerator	2031	8	2039
Injector w. e+/e- sources	Accelerator	2032	5	2037
Transfer lines	Accelerator	2033	5	2038
Adaptation of CERN machines	Accelerator	2032	5	2037
Electricity infrastructure	Infrastructure	2031	7	2038
Cooling and Ventilation	Infrastructure	2033	5	2038
Transport and Installation	Infrastructure	2031	8	2039
Other tech. infrastructures	Infrastructure	2034	8	2042
Experiment 1	Experiment	2034	7	2041
Experiment 2	Experiment	2034	7	2041
Civil engineering construction	Civil Engineering	2030	9	2039
Operation developments	Operation	2042	11	2053

3.4.2. Operating expenditures

Operating costs include all disbursements (both in-kind and outflows) needed to operate and maintain the FCC-ee research infrastructure during the entire project time horizon. The StR-ESFRI guidelines on cost estimation of research infrastructures (2019) provide a reference framework for the identification and measurement of costs of any research infrastructure. In general, operating costs tend to be constant when the project is running at full capacity, but during the start-up and launch phases there is a ramp up period which can last some years. Typical operating costs of a research infrastructures, which will be considered for the FCC-ee analysis, include:

- **Personnel (labour cost):** estimates will be based on the average costs of scientists, engineers, post-doc researchers, students, technicians, administrative staff involved in the project. These costs will be based on average gross salaries in the countries participating in the project, including the compulsory social security payments and overheads paid by the employers (in line with the European Commission's guidelines, 2014)³.
- **Maintenance and repair:** include the equipment and materials costs necessary for keeping the buildings and the facilities in good condition, including expenditure to fix broken parts and replacement of spare parts. They do not include major replacement costs of fixed assets already accounted as capital investment. The maintenance and repair costs can be assumed to be a percentage share of the annual investment costs and will be based on consensus agreement with different technical subsystem groups. Typical values range from 1% to 10% per year of the investment costs, depending on the technology of the subsystem with a peak of the distribution in the 2% to 2.5% range (the typical experience value for maintenance repair of machines with moving parts is 37% of investment cost over useful life period). Maintenance and repair costs will therefore be considered for the individual subsystems of the project at a high level (e.g. cryogenics, magnets, radiofrequency, cooling and ventilation, transport and handling, electricity distribution and powering, beam diagnostics, computing and controls, other technical systems, general services).
- **Utilities and services:** include the energy (electricity, fuel) costs associated to the project and other specific services (water, heating, computing and telecommunication, etc.) purchased by third parties.
- **Consumables** refer to any raw or (semi)processed materials and components necessary of the project operation, including their transport costs from source of supply to the facility. For the FCC, they refer to helium, nitrogen, working gases, office materials and other materials that are needed for day-to-day operation.
- **Rent of building or equipment:** this cost item may not be particularly significant for the FCC project, but there may be some costs associated to the land and subsurface volumes.
- **Management and administration:** these expenditures can be assumed to be a fixed share of the labour costs (overheads) required to properly run the project on a daily basis. A flat-rate overhead will be defined for use in the forecast calculations for this item. For instance, the EU projects foresee a fixed overhead⁴ of 25% for so called "indirect costs" which relate to expenses that are not directly linked to the subject work, but which are indispensable for the proper project implementation of H2020 co-funded project. Examples include costs for offices, postage, insurance, office supplies, general telephone and internet usage, heating, electricity, accounting and legal services, human resource services, clerks.⁵
- **Communication and promotion:** this item includes promotional campaigns and other outreach expenditures associated to the FCC-ee project.
- **Other expenses:** these items collect additional relevant annual expenses that can be directly attributed to the project such as environmental accompanying measures, costs for safety and security, scientific conference and workshop organization.

³ For instance, the Eurostat service reports on an average of 24.5% of non-wage costs that are typically added on top of average gross salaries. For more information, see https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Wages_and_labour_costs#Labour_cost_components.

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf

⁵ Attention will be given to avoid possible double-counting with other cost items (e.g. those related to utilities and services).

3.5. SOCIAL DISCOUNT RATE (SDR)

3.5.1. Context and rationale

The FCC-ee project schedule reveals that costs and benefits occur at different points in time and are spread over a long-term period; therefore, there is the challenge to express them in a consistent and comparable way so as to be evaluated at the time the present assessment is carried out. The SDR is a parameter used in the economic analysis of investment projects when inter-temporal investment decisions⁶ have to be taken. The SDR **allows assigning a present (discounted) monetary value, expressed in today's value, to costs and benefits that occur over time** to reflect their value at the current time. The discounting formula is as follows:

$$\text{Present Value of Impact } A = \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{A_t}{(1 + \text{SDR})^t}$$

where:

- t is one year of the time horizon, running from 1 (first year of the analysis) to n (end of time horizon)
- A_t is the value of impact A at time t
- SDR is the social discount rate value adopted for the project.

3.5.2. Interpretation of the SDR

The SDR reflects how society values well-being today versus well-being in the future. This has important implications for resource allocation in investment projects. Higher values of SDR reflect the fact that people have preferences for consuming resources today instead of investing them and thus postponing consumption in the future. In this case, society's preferences are for increasing welfare today through increased consumption of products and services, instead of reducing it today for being better off in the future. In contrast, lower values of the parameter indicate that society is more ready to renounce part of its consumption today in favour of investing it for future benefits. The limit is a zero SDR, which means that society has no time preferences in choosing between present or future consumption.

The SDR is therefore related to society's preferences. Its value depends on many factors both at the country level, e.g. the level of economic development, and at the international level, such as global economic crises and health-related shocks influencing the population probability to survive and being able to consume in the future. Empirical evidence from the economic literature⁷ shows that the SDR is higher in developing countries, often characterised by a GDP higher growth rate, than in countries with more mature economic systems and higher mortality rates (people are more willing to invest in the future since their life expectancy is higher). Also, in turbulent times caused for instance by economic downturns and health-related shocks, uncertainty about the future increases and current consumption reduces, leading to lower SDRs as compared to normal times. In line with this argument, and to mention one example of SDR estimated for the period 2014-2020, the European Commission recommended that a 5% SDR is used for the appraisal of major investment projects in the Cohesion countries (EU Member States with a lower GDP level) and a 3% SDR for the other EU Member States.⁸

3.5.3. Project SDR value

SDR values can be estimated with different methods.⁹ One of the methods most used by international organisations is based on the social rate of time preference (SRTP),¹⁰ which considers the social preferences

⁶ When decision is taken today about using resources that are not available now, but will be in a future time.

⁷ See for instance Zhuang, L., (2007), Lopez, H. (2008).

⁸ European Commission (2014).

⁹ The social rate of return on private investments (SRRI), the social rate of time preference (SRTP), the weighted average approach (WAA), the shadow price of capital. See European Commission (2014) for details. Moreover, a more detailed explanation of the rationale for using the SDR as well as of the different approaches for calculating it is reported in Catalano and Pancotti (2021).

¹⁰ The theoretical foundation of the SRTP is the Ramsey–Cass–Koopmans model or Ramsey growth model (Ramsey, 1928; Cass, 1965; Koopmans, 1965). It is a neoclassical model of economic growth based primarily on the work of Ramsey (1928). According to the model, there is a social planner (the government) that solves an inter-temporal optimization problem of social utility with respect to consumption, considering the welfare of both current and future generations. The Ramsey–Cass–Koopmans model differs from the Solow–Swan (Solow, 1956; Swan, 1956) model in that the choice of consumption is explicitly microfounded at a point in time and so endogenizes the savings rate.

and welfare of both current and future generations. Specifically, **the SRTP captures three main arguments to justify the need for discounting:**

- i. the pure time preference of consumers: consumers prefer to receive the same amount of goods and services sooner rather than later;
- ii. the assumption of a steadily increasing level of income and consumption for the society over time;
- iii. the opportunity cost of resources: the allocation of any type of resources (money, persons, time) to a project represents a cost to society, because of the potential missed opportunities foregone by choosing to use those resources for one investment over another.

For the purpose of this analysis, the SDR is set according to the SRTP approach with the following formula:

$$SDR = SRTP = p + \varepsilon * g$$

where:

- p is *the pure time preference*. It captures the impatience and myopia of people to consume as soon as possible instead of delaying consumption to the future. It can be proxied with the annual crude death rate of the population, assuming that consumption is anticipated when the risk of death or human race extinction increases. In this project we use Eurostat data for year 2019 to obtain that value.
- g is the (expected) per-capita growth rate of consumption. It is proxied by the real growth rate of the pre-capita GDP under the assumption that the GDP properly reflects the dynamics of consumption over time. We calculate it by using IMF forecast covering the period 2002-2021, which takes into account the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the world's economy.
- ε is *the elasticity of marginal utility of consumption*. This parameter measures the extent to which the satisfaction (utility) from additional consumption decreases as the level of consumption rises. When the current level of consumption provides "saturation", increasing consumption even more would still provide satisfaction but to a lower extent. Assuming there is some growth ($g > 0$), consumption has a lower unit utility in the future. The term ($\varepsilon * g$) will still be positive but ε decreases as g increases. There are a number of methods to estimate ε . The most common ones are those based on (progressivity of) taxation models, which influence people's demand for goods and services: as income increases, taxes increases more than proportionally and available income for consumption decreases. We estimate the elasticity of marginal utility of consumption based on social preferences revealed by taxation. We used the 2020 OECD Taxation Database to determine ε .

By applying the formula above, we estimated the SDR in each country that contributes to the CERN budget today, including CERN Members States and Associated Countries.¹¹ We then estimated the average of the SDR in each country, weighted by the respective contribution to the CERN budget. **The resulting SDR value is 2%**¹² (see Table 2 below).

¹¹ Data are missing for some CERN contributors – Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Romania, Israel, Serbia, India, Pakistan and Ukraine. Our estimates refer to the countries with contribute altogether to 95% of CERN budget. Countries with Observer status – including Japan, the Russian Federation and the United States of America, as well as the European Union, JINR and UNESCO – were not included in this calculation since not contributing to CERN budget.

¹² A detailed explanation of the assumptions underlying the calculation of the SDR, including also comparison between areas in EU can be found in Catalano and Pancotti (2021).

Table 2. Estimation of the SDR for the FCC-ee socio-economic impact analysis.

Country	p (annual crude death % rate 2019)	g (GDP annual growth % rate; 2020-2021)	e (elasticity % rate; 2020)	Unweighted SDR	% Contribution to the CERN budget (2020)
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	5
<i>CERN Member States</i>					
Austria	0.94	0.71	1.48	1.98	2.1
Belgium	0.95	0.74	1.68	2.19	2.6
Bulgaria	1.55	3.96	--	--	0.3
Czechia	1.05	2.25	1.30	3.97	1.0
Denmark	0.93	0.76	1.44	2.03	1.7
Finland	0.98	0.88	1.63	2.41	1.3
France	0.91	0.52	1.52	1.70	13.6
Germany	1.13	0.95	1.33	2.39	20.3
Greece	1.17	-0.22	1.69	0.80	1.0
Hungary	1.33	2.42	1.00	3.75	0.6
Italy	1.06	-0.40	1.81	0.34	10.0
Netherlands	0.88	0.76	1.98	2.39	4.4
Poland	1.08	3.59	1.08	4.95	2.7
Portugal	1.09	0.47	1.62	1.86	1.1
Romania	1.34	4.54	--	--	1.1
Slovakia	0.98	3.46	1.32	5.55	0.5
Spain	0.88	0.42	1.65	1.58	6.9
Sweden	0.86	1.12	1.68	2.73	2.5
UK	0.90	0.59	1.65	1.88	15.5
Switzerland	0.79	0.78	1.57	2.02	4.0
Israel	--	1.37	2.13	--	1.8
Norway	0.76	0.63	1.47	1.68	2.3
<i>Associate Member States in the pre-stage to Membership</i>					
Cyprus	0.71	0.70	--	--	0.1
Serbia	1.46	3.85	--	--	0.2
Slovenia	0.99	1.75	1.23	3.15	0.1
<i>Associate Member States</i>					
Lithuania	1.37	4.93	1.28	7.67	0.1
Turkey	0.53	3.91	1.33	5.71	0.5
Croatia	1.27	1.88	--	--	0.1
India	--	5.37	--	--	1.3
Pakistan	--	1.92	--	--	0.2
Ukraine	1.93	2.65	--	--	0.1
Weighted average SDR			2.00		100%

*Note: *based on 2020 Annual Contributions to CERN budget (<https://fap-dep.web.cern.ch/rpc/2020-annual-contributions-cern-budget>); Countries with Observer status – including Japan, the Russian Federation and the United States of America, as well as the European Union, JINR and UNESCO – were not included in this calculation since not contributing to CERN budget.*

3.6. THE COUNTERFACTUAL SCENARIO

3.6.1. Context, definition and rationale

The socio-economic impact model for FCC-ee adopts an incremental approach for the analysis of the impacts. This means that **both the costs and benefits of the project are expressed in incremental terms compared to a situation in which the project is not implemented. This scenario is called the “counterfactual scenario” (CFS)** (Florio, 2014). It is prescribed for use by different national and international operative guidelines that foresee an incremental impact assessment approach for the evaluation of public investments in different sectors, such as environment, road transport, and others. Countries with the longest traditions of project appraisal include the UK (HM Treasury, 2018), France (Quinet, 2007, 2013), the United States of America (US General Accounting Office, 2007).

This method aims to grasp the “net” change, i.e. the causally related changes that can be specifically attributed to the project. The changes can be positive and negative.

The choice of the CFS requires a careful examination and implies defining what would happen in the absence of the project. Different options are possible. In some cases, when the new facility is completely new (‘green field’ investment) the without-the-project scenario can be a ‘zero-based’ scenario. In other words, the incremental scenario coincides with the ‘with-the-project’ scenario. Examples of *green field* research infrastructures are the National Hadrontherapy Centre for Cancer Treatment (CNAO) based in Pavia, or the Jules Horowitz Reactor (JHR) built on the Cadarache site in France. In other cases, when investments are made to either substantially upgrade or reconvert an existing facility or at least use and leverage on pre-existing infrastructures, the counterfactual scenario should include the costs and benefits to operate and maintain it at a level that keeps it operable (this scenario is referred to as ‘business as usual’ or ‘do-nothing’) and minor investments that are programmed to avoid interruption of the service (do-minimum). Examples of *incremental* research infrastructures are the High Luminosity Large Hadron Collider at CERN and the upgrade of the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility in Grenoble. The FCC-ee project also responds to the definition of incremental infrastructure: while being a completely new infrastructure, it is expected to make some use of existing infrastructures (e.g. electricity and water distribution infrastructures, offices, workshops, telecommunications, particle accelerators, collaborative working spaces, conference and meeting facilities, visitor centres, administrative infrastructures put in place by CERN over several decades).

In-depth discussions with science specialists involved in the project design and with independent professionals providing sufficiently neutral judgments are fundamental to choosing a proper counterfactual scenario.

3.6.2. Counterfactual scenario of the FCC-ee project

The results of the discussions with members of the particle accelerator and high-energy research community, with project external scientists and economists led to the preference of selecting the “**Business-as-usual (BAU) continuation at CERN**” scenario as the most credible counterfactual scenario for the FCC-ee. When analysing the costs and benefits of the FCC-ee project, we assume that the existing HL-LHC will continue its operations until its expected end of life, estimated around 2040 (Bastianin and Florio, 2018). The possibility to continue with minor capital investments to the existing infrastructure to further prolong its lifetime has been considered not credible, since the science opportunities through extended operation would be negligible.

The BAU scenario adopted for the socio-economic impact assessment is coherent with the “evolution without-the-project scenario” applied for the environmental evaluation.

In the estimation of all benefits for the FCC-ee project, we will pay attention to consider only those ones that would be generated by the FCC-ee project, but that are not already directly attributed to the HL-LHC. For instance, the cost-benefit analysis of the HL-LHC (Bastianin and Florio, 2018) identified some benefits that would materialise after the project’s end of life, until 2080 (they refer to cultural and educational benefits for society). These benefits will not be attributed to the FCC-ee project, even if they occur in the same time period.

In contrast, we will for instance attribute to the FCC-ee project the **decommissioning cost of the LHC**, which would take place in the without-the-project scenario. These costs relate to:

- cost of dismantling and disposal of the collider and, if possible re-use of elements;
- cost of dismantling and disposal of the experiment facilities and, if possible re-use of elements;
- cost of at least partial re-naturalisation of the surface sites;
- cost of continued maintenance of the infrastructures that remain (e.g. tunnel) to assure a safe environment;
- cost of additional maintenance and modification costs associated.

Since the HL-LHC infrastructure may be of use for future particle colliders at CERN, the decommissioning cost will be avoided and can therefore be accounted as "virtual benefits" of FCC-ee.

A first estimate was made by CERN in 2018¹³. Cost estimates depend on the agreements of costs for the acceptance of radioactive waste for further use by the two host states and are therefore subject to evolution. The existing estimate is considered sufficient for inclusion in the cost-benefit estimates.

¹³ M. Magistris, M. Widorski, H. Vincke, “Radioactive waste estimates for the FCC project”, CERN-RP-2017-054-REPORTS-TN, EDMS 1992036, V2.0, 6 December 2018, limited access.

4. ASSUMPTIONS, DATA & METHODS FOR THE MODEL

4.1. IMPACT PATHWAY 1: THE VALUE OF SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTS FOR THE SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY

4.1.1. Definition of the benefit

This impact pathway explores what is probably the most immediate benefit that the project will deliver: scientific products. The definition of scientific products refers to any kind of **citable publication** including preprints, articles in peer-reviewed journals, working papers, books, conference and workshop contributions and other documents. While acknowledging that this proxy may be imperfect, this approach is largely consolidated in the literature.¹⁴

As explained in Griniece et al. (2020), this pathway follows the traditional idea of “knowledge push” where research infrastructures generate scientific publications or similar products either directly or via users. **These are, in turn, cited by others and eventually become part of a new body of knowledge.** That body of knowledge later finds (conscious or unconscious) recognition within a broader research community and society. Final recipients of the knowledge generated may further translate it into economic benefits or apply it to societal problem-solving efforts.

While the objective of FCC-ee is advancing knowledge about the fundamentals of the Universe, **this pathway does not measure the overall social value of the knowledge produced in terms of potential future practical use (if any).** As discussed in section 2.1, forecasting the full value of knowledge creation relating to fundamental scientific research is not sufficiently reliable, since societal applications and the times when such applications occur cannot be forecasted. Rather, the estimation will focus on the first stages of the “knowledge push” impacts, i.e. **value of the scientific products produced by scientists for further use in scientific research** based on actual observation of this process in ongoing fundamental science projects. In so doing, this pathway takes the perspective of the scientists, engineers and researchers as “producers” and “consumers” of scientific products that the FCC-ee research programme is likely to generate, but it does not consider the ultimate impacts on other members of society.

4.1.2. Assumptions

The estimation of the future benefit of scientific products takes, as a starting point, the model previously adopted to estimate the value of scientific outputs of LHC (whose main parameters are illustrated in the Table below). Different adjustments will be used to improve the estimation for the FCC-ee impact study.

First, **actual data on the scientific publications relating to the LHC research programme are collected.** They serve as benchmark for the estimates of future science products. In this context, scientific products include:

1. citable articles in peer-reviewed scientific journals,
2. citable working papers/not peer-reviewed articles in document servers,
3. citable preprints,
4. citable conference proceedings,
5. scientific books for academic use,
6. contributed chapters in edited books,
7. citable conference and workshop presentations and posters.

This collection of science products includes so called “**Level 0**” **publications directly produced by scientists, engineers and other researchers who participate in the research programme.** They serve as “corpus” for the creation of further science products. Level 0 publications document knowledge acquired during the design, construction and operation phases of the science programme. They are identified by searching keywords in publication metadata (title, keyword, abstract, author list). Then, “**Level 1**” **science products are identified by searching for science products that cite Level 0 products** and “**Level 2**” **science products citing Level 1 products. Citations are used to proxy the impact of a scientific publication in the scientific community.**

¹⁴ Martin, 1996; JASPERS, 2015; Carrazza et al., 2016; Florio and Sirtori, 2016; Florio et al., 2016.

Figure 6. Illustration of the publications used in the analysis based on a multi-level citation analysis.

The data are analysed via state-of-the art bibliometric techniques. They might include the computation of further impact measures (e.g. impact factors), indicators on the degree of multi-disciplinarity of a publication, and indicators that measure the level of collaboration that led to a publication (by looking for example at the affiliations of the authors).

Tracking past records permits creating a basis for the forecast of future scientific products using a model which makes assumptions on the expected number of authors of these publications and their productivity (number of publications per year).

Once the data on past records are analysed and estimates for future publications are generated, their **benefits in terms of monetary value will be estimated**. In the literature, two methods are documented to estimate the social value of a benefit:

- by taking the consumer perspective, considering the market price, the consume (i.e. read) time value or the willingness to pay for the good, or
- by taking the producer perspective by looking at the production costs of producing that good.

Previous works assumed that market prices including the subscription fees of journals and the price paid by researchers for making available a paper in Open Access form do not provide a good indication for the socio-economic value of scientific products, since many scientific products are available free of charge.

The **production cost approach** was the preferred option for the estimation of the social value of scientific products. This is also the approach applied in the evaluation of the LHC and HL-LHC. This approach relies on the economic concept of opportunity costs and value of time. Anyone's time is a valuable resource. The decision of a scientist to spend time on writing an article, downloading and reading someone else's paper or book, implies the use of his/her time in this activity and the lost opportunity of using it for a different activity (e.g. another research project, teaching activities, etc.). **The scientist's annual gross salary¹⁵ divided by the number of hours worked can be taken as a proxy of the value (benefit) for society of his/her time.**

Following this approach, estimating the value of scientific products generated by the FCC-ee projects requires using data on wages of scientific personnel and other researchers involved in the project and making some assumptions on the number of hours spent to write and cite a publication or any other scientific product.

Since scientists producing Level 0 papers are part of the personnel working on the project, their salary is accounted both on the cost side (operating expenditure) and on the benefit side (proxy of the value of scientific products). For this reason, the socio-economic value of Level 0 products partly cancels out with the costs of personnel. Table 3 below shows the steps and assumptions adopted for the estimation of the scientific products benefits of the LHC, focusing on Level 1 and Level 2 papers.

Starting from the assumptions used in previous impact assessments (Table 3), we will consider different ways to fine-tune the methodological approach and underlying assumptions, with specific reference to the FCC-ee project. The value of Level 0 papers can be estimated as a benefit to obtain the full value of the scientific production benefits. In order to make the results of the FCC-ee project directly comparable with the results of

¹⁵ Including overheads and social security payments.

previous studies on the LHC and HL LHC, we will also compute the value of scientific products without including the Level 0 products, whose value is offset by the corresponding costs of personnel included in the project operating expenditure.

Table 3. Steps and parameters used to calculate the value of scientific products for the LHC project.

Step	Description	Key parameter used for the analysis of the LHC
1	Quantification of the number of scientific products produced by scientists and researchers working on the FCC-ee (level 0 products, P0)	The number of available scientific products related to the LHC were extracted from existing databases of publications, pre-prints, working papers, etc. (INSPIRE http://inspirehep.net/). A double exponential model was applied to forecast the future number of scientific products and their time profile (2013-2025). The model applied, based on Bacchiocchi and Montobbio (2010), was in this form: $E(L0t) = \alpha_1 \cdot \alpha_2 \cdot \exp(-\beta_1(T-t)) \cdot (1 - \exp(-\beta_2(T-t)))$. The following assumptions were made on the key parameters: Size of the scientific community, i.e. assumed number of scientists and researchers producing scientific outputs $\alpha_1 = 65,000$; Assumed average H-index $\alpha_2 = 2$; $\beta_1 = 0.18$; $\beta_2 = 0.008$; Years of the model $T = 50$; First year of estimation $t = 2006$.
2	Quantification of the number of scientific products citing level 0 products (level 1 products, P1)	The number of scientific products citing Level 0 products were extracted from existing databases for the years 1993-2012 (INSPIRE http://inspirehep.net/). The future number of citations (2013-2050) was forecasted by assuming a declining number of citations for each Level 0 product, which follows the time profile of future P0 outputs. No new spikes of citations (such as the one generated from the discovery of the Higgs boson) were assumed.
3	Quantification of the number of downloads of level 0 products	The number of past downloads of Level 0 products in the field of High Energy Physics products were extracted from the ArXiv document server (operated by Cornell University). The future number of downloads (2013-2050) was estimated by assuming a fixed average number of downloads for each P0. Based on historical data, it was assumed that each paper generated 64 downloads on average.
4	Quantification of the number of scientific products citing level 1 products (level 2 products, P2)	The number of second-level citations to Level 1 products is estimated by assuming that each level 1 product generates an average of 4 citations in other publications, pre-prints, working paper, etc. The number of Level 2 products was forecasted for the period 2013-2050. No new spikes of citations (such as the one generated from the discovery of the Higgs boson) were assumed.
5	Estimation of the number of references included in citing scientific products	Based on the analysis of historical data of publications, it was assumed an average number of bibliographic references in the citing publications equal to 35.
6	Estimation of the socio-economic value of level 0 scientific products, level 1 citations and downloads, and level 2 products	The socio-economic value was estimated by considering the value of the time needed to produce the scientific products, citing them at level 1 and level 2, and downloading them. Assuming an average yearly salary of 59 289 EUR for each author (based on Payscale and other sources of salaries for scientists), the following parameters were assumed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unit production costs for each scientific product: 11 011 EUR • Unit production costs for level 1 scientific products that is attributed to the LHC: 11 011 EUR divided by the number of references included. An average value of 315 EUR for each level 1 paper is considered. • Unit production cost of citations (including the time for reading and citing or downloading a scientific product): 99 EUR. Note: these values serve as starting point and production costs will be adjusted based on the labour costs used for the operation cost estimates.
5	Computation of the total value of scientific products	The following formula was applied to estimate the total economic value of scientific products of LHC: $V = \left[V \left(\frac{P_1}{k_1} \right) + V \left(\frac{P_2}{k_2} \right) + \dots + V \left(\frac{P_n}{k_n} \right) \right] + [V(Q_0) + V(Q_1)]$ Where $i = 0, 1, 2$ indicates the various waves of scientific products' production, where '0' is used to refer to level 0 products; '1' to level 1 products; '2' to level 2 products. P_i is the total social cost of producing scientific products of wave i , computed as the number of papers of level i multiplied by their socio-economic value.

		Q_i is total socio-economic value of citations received by papers of wave i from papers of wave $i + 1$. Note that, by definition, the number of quotations received by papers of wave i is equivalent to the number of papers produced in wave $i + 1$. k_i is the number of references included in each paper.
6	Application of the net present value formula	Discount the total economic value using the Social Discount Rate.

Source: Authors based on Florio et al. (2016).

4.2. IMPACT PATHWAY 2: EDUCATION AND TRAINING

4.2.1. Definition of the benefit

This impact pathway explores the benefit of human capital formation. Training new generations of scientists and engineers has in the past been identified as one of the main benefits of the LHC research programme. It accounted for around one third of the total socio-economic benefits of the LHC. The FCC-ee is expected to build human capital by improving the skills and career development of people working on the project. Past studies have shown that this benefit translates into new skills and increased labour productivity. **The benefit can be quantitatively estimated by a lifetime salary premium with respect to persons who do not participate in such a type of project.** Several investigations provide evidence of the existence that benefit (Bianchin et al., 2019; Catalano et al., 2018; Camporesi, 2001).

In addition to on-the-job training, there may be other activities fostering education and training of future researchers. They include, for instance, the apprenticeship programmes for Swiss high-school students, the national and international teacher programmes carried out by CERN¹⁶ (11 414 teachers in 19 years, 600-900 teachers per year in all programmes, order of 50 teachers per year participate in an international two-week residential programme¹⁷ and in 4-6 days lasting national programmes), high-school student master classes for about 13 000 high school students organised by the experiments in ten years (~ 1 300 pupils per year for 1-2 days per class)¹⁸, offering professional development programmes for teachers to keep up-to-date with the latest development in particle physics and related areas, and other specific training activities existing today and potentially developed for FCC-ee. Moreover, as was the case with LEP and LHC physics knowledge gain, the results of scientific research carried out at the FCC-ee could eventually feed into the syllabus and teaching materials of university and high-school education programmes, and contribute at improving the understanding about the universe inner working and the origin of humankind of the future generations of students and, perhaps, scientists. All these benefits are part of the general impact pathway related to education and training, but their economic valuation requires different specific methodologies and data. This impact pathway will primarily focus on analysing the training and education effects of on-the-job training carried out during the FCC-ee lifetime for students and early-stage researchers. **Economic quantification of the benefits will focus on the human capital effects for people that spend a limited work period in the FCC-ee project.** Methodologies previously developed and tested in the context of other research infrastructures will be used for this analysis. If time and resources will allow, other benefits for students and your researchers will also be explored.

4.2.2. Assumptions

A research infrastructure typically employs **four main groups of people** under a variety of contractual conditions:

- 1) **scientists and engineers** (including postdoctoral researchers);
- 2) **technical personnel**;
- 3) **administrative** and support personnel and
- 4) **students** at different education levels (including trainees).

¹⁶ For statistics and materials see <https://indico.cern.ch/category/5886/>.

¹⁷ <https://home.cern/news/news/knowledge-sharing/cerns-international-high-school-teacher-programme-turns-20>.

¹⁸ International masterclasses, <https://physicsmasterclasses.org>.

The **focus** of our analysis will be **on early-career researchers** (apprentices, trainees, technical students, doctoral students, post-doctoral researchers, associated members of personnel up to a cut-off age).

These people are important for the development and operation of the research infrastructure. They perform data analysis, design and construction of experiments, software development, scientific and technical publication production, testing and qualification, laboratory work and many other relevant activities. During their work period in the project, they gain diverse technical skills, increase their problem-solving capacity, learn teamwork, management and communication capabilities, acquire social capital thanks to the access to a wide network of contacts in the scientific community and benefit from reputational effects thanks to their direct participation in the activities of a highly-recognised research centre. These effects, in turn, lead to better job opportunities and a “premium” on their future salaries. This premium reflects the **marginal salary increase, gained by a former early-stage researcher who has spent time at the FCC-ee, compared to a salary which would have been earned without such an experience.**

Previous estimates of this benefit for the LHC revealed that the **premium ranges between 5 % and 12 %** of the average salary, depending on the future professional sector, type of tasks carried out and skills acquired (Catalano et al., 2021; Camporesi et al., 2017).

Six steps are necessary to estimate the value of training. They are summarized in Table 4. The assumptions for the calculation of the key parameters are discussed as follows. **The assumptions and values of the parameters reported in this section are preliminary and need to be fine-tuned in an update of this document.** To this end, an online survey targeted to former and current researchers was launched by CERN in June 2020 and is currently still ongoing. The survey will provide additional evidence to validate and fine-tuned the parameters of our model.

Table 4. Steps and parameters to calculate the value of training impact.

Step	Description	Key Parameter
1	Forecast the number of people per year who will benefit from the salary premium. It is calculated as a share of the total number of people involved in the FCC-ee scientific programme.	The number of students and early career researchers to be considered depends on two parameters: Age cut off: 30 years Distribution of duration of stay at CERN: min 1 year; max 5 years
2	Determine the professional sector in which students and early-career researchers will likely work after the CERN experience.	The following distribution is used: Academia and research (53%) Industry and finance (32%) Public administration, incl. non-profit (15%)
3	Definition of salary functions. They represent the base salary of people in the different professional sectors.	Salary functions were estimated as logarithmic functions depending on the length of the job market careers, i.e. the years of experience in the labour market (X). They were estimated for the following sectors: Academia and research: $Y=28,270+21,966*\ln(X)$; Industry and finance: $Y=26,987+27,964*\ln(X)$; Public ad, incl. non-profit: $Y=26,796+30,552*\ln(X)$ All sectors: $Y=27,799+ 26,251*\ln(X)$
4	Estimate the length of the job market careers of CERN people	The length of the total active working life to be applied is on average 39.5 years, with the following probability distribution: 39 years (66%) 40 years (17%) 41/42 years (17%)
5	Estimate the salary premium	According to recent studies in this field, it is estimated in the following ranges: From 5% to 12% (Camporesi et al., 2017) From 5% to 11% (Catalano et al., 2017). The value of this parameters will be fine-tuned with survey results and the distribution shape remains to be defined.
6	Application of the net present value formula	Social discount rate: 2% (see section 3.5)

The first step is to estimate the number of people per year who are likely to benefit from the salary premium until the end of the FCC-ee operation phase. This number is a fraction of the number of the people as reported in Section 3.3. For this study, we consider that **only students and early-career researchers including post-doctoral employees are beneficiaries of a salary premium**. It is understood that **this leads to an underestimate of the impact**. However, this assumption yields a reliable estimate of the impact without the need to include potentially unreliable information about the effects on experienced personnel which has not been traced so far. The exact number to be used for the forecast remains to be determined by analysis of the existing data. Two criteria will be considered as cut off condition:

- **Only people younger than 30 years will be considered for the lifetime salary premium.** The economic literature on human capital accumulation (Psacharopoulos and Patrinos, 2018; Lemieux, 2006; Mincer, 1974) suggests that formal education, generally acquired during the young age, is a key determinant for future career paths, including the level of the salary.
- **Only people who spend at least one year on the project and no longer than five years will be included in the analysis.** Activities in a high-tech research project turned out to be a human and social capital incubator. People acquire knowledge, skills and competencies that are highly valued in the labour market. Based on previous studies,¹⁹ the level of skill acquisition is a function of the duration of stay at the research project. This cut-off condition excludes the share of staff who remains at CERN for longer time periods.

The second step is to determine the sector in which students and early-career researchers will be likely to work after the experience in the project. Based on existing studies (Bianchin et al., 2019; Florio et al., 2016), we assume the following preliminary distribution (to be fine-tuned with a survey):

- 53% remain in the academia and research sector;
- 32% move to the industry and finance sectors;
- 15% move to the public administration sector, including non-profit organisations.

The third step concerns the establishment of the lifetime salary evolution functions for each of the above indicated sectors. The project induced salary premium will then be applied to those functions. Following the literature on human capital accumulation (Psacharopoulos and Patrinos, 2018; Lemieux, 2006; Mincer, 1974), which considers the salary evolution predominantly as a function of the active working years, Table 5 shows the formulas of the distributions of salaries by sector. Salary functions and their parameters are reported for the three sectors: academia and research, industry/finance and public administration. A fourth function groups all three sectors in one single salary evolution function. It can be used as a reference for the salary evolution for those people for which information about the working sector is incomplete or difficult to forecast. Annex 7.3 reports all the details about how the salary functions were determined.

Table 5. Salary functions and key parameters by sector in 2019 CHF.

Parameters	Academia/research	Industry/finance	Public administration	All sectors
Salary functions*	$Y=28,270+21,966*\ln(X)$	$Y=26,987+27,964*\ln(X)$	$Y=26,796+30,552*\ln(X)$	$Y=27,799+26,251*\ln(X)$
Mean	43,336	53,271	55,263	53,496
Median	36,780	44,496	46,761	44,583
Std Dev	27,920	34,540	33,189	36,142
Min	6,621	1,366	3,337	1,366
Max	114,686	278,364	178,686	278,364
Skewness**	0.99	2.26	1.46	1.53
Kurtosis**	3.36	11.3	5.21	6.46

Source: Authors' elaboration based on Glassdoor data.

¹⁹ Catalano et al. (2021); Camporesi et al. (2017); Camporesi (2001).

*Note: * Y stands for “annual salary”; X stands for “number of years of working experiences”. **The skewness of the normal distribution is zero, while the Kurtosis is 3.0.*

The fourth step is to estimate the duration of the active working period of people after their project experience. It corresponds the time people benefit from the salary premium. Based on *ad-hoc* analysis reported in Annex 7.4, we assume that the active working life of people leaving the project is on **average 39.5 years**, with the following probability distribution: 39 years (66%); 40 years (17%); 41/42 years (17%). This means that on average students and early-researchers entering the labour market in 2030 are expected to receive the salary premium until 2069. The cohort entering in 2050 is likely to enjoy their salary premium until 2089. The details are discussed in Annex 7.4.

The fifth step is estimating the value of the lifetime salary premium. Camporesi et al. (2017) and Catalano et al. (2021) explored the contribution of spending a period of research and/or work at the Large Hadron Collider of CERN to the expected future lifelong salary of early-career researchers. By applying primary data collected through a survey to CERN Alumni, a survey to team leaders who supervised early-career researchers at CERN, and secondary data salary information, the **salary premium is between 5% to 12% compared to persons who earn a doctorate degree without participating abroad in a research infrastructure related project. The shape of the distribution remains to be defined.** Findings show that an experience-based learning process at CERN is instrumental in developing skills that are demanded by the labour market; in contrast, the CERN networking and reputational effects seems to play a minor role in shaping career development paths, including the salary. In the framework of the FCC-ee socio-economic impact model, we will use the on-going survey to confirm and fine-tune such findings.

The last step is to apply the net present value formula to evaluate the value of training benefit considering the social discount rate discussed in Section 3.5.

4.3. IMPACT PATHWAY 3: INDUSTRIAL SPILLOVERS

4.3.1. Definition of the benefit

This pathway explores effects that the project is expected to generate on private companies. A wealth of literature and empirical evidence exists documenting the channels through which big-science and research infrastructure investments generate industrial spillovers (Sirtori et al., 2019; Florio et al., 2018; Griniece et al. (2020); Autio et al., 2004). Previous works on the LHC and the HL-LHC projects found that the socio-economic benefits generated through **procurement activities for the construction and operation of the research infrastructure accounts for over one third of all the project benefits**. When supplier companies work closely with the research infrastructure and its designers to develop innovative or high technological intensive products or services, they exchange ideas and knowledge, feeding the creation of new processes, products and services that supplier companies can also exploit in other markets (see Castelnovo et al. 2018, Florio et al. 2018, and Sirtori et al 2019). The impact pathways will focus on the industrial benefits generated by the procurement for the FCC-ee project, especially during its construction phase. This benefit is also related to the idea of the **FCC-ee as a platform of “Open Innovation”**: the project can be used by companies as a platform **to bring their technologies to higher maturity or quality levels, to test them out, to find solutions to costly or time-intensive issues, which could eventually bring them additional market opportunities**. This investigation will be complemented by the analysis of territorial benefits of procurement (described in section 5.1). If time and resources will permit, we could consider additional possible benefits to the industry, namely:

- The socio-economic value of **procurement during the project operation**, also including any possible benefit directly generated by the FCC-ee on **service suppliers**.
- The **benefits of technological innovation** developed by companies not through their procurement activity, but **thanks to other spillovers of knowledge generated by the FCC-ee**. While it is unlikely that fundamental physics can directly translate into industrial/commercial innovations, it is possible that some research carried out by scientists and engineers on the machine construction could inspire new ideas in the private companies to improve their own machines or to invent new commercial instruments and applications. A possible approach to capture this benefit is to search for patents or other forms of intellectual property protection filed by companies that cite scientific products related to the FCC-ee and attribute an economic value to such innovations.

4.3.2. Assumptions

Procurement activities may generate technological spillovers and learning opportunities for supplier firms. Procurement contracts for a fundamental science project may challenge firms to supply new, improved and cutting-edge products, services and technological solutions. These effects are likely to positively impact the innovativeness, productivity and profitability of supplier firms as well as the reputation in their served markets. Literature shows that it is especially the procurement of higher technological intensity that is associated with some socio-economic benefit that goes beyond the value of the procurement contracts.

To quantify the industrial spillover impacts from procurement, we apply the following steps:

1. Following previous literature (Schmied, 1977; Bianchi-Streit et al., 1984), we **estimated a sales multiplier** related to the CERN LHC procurement. It is calculated **as the ratio between suppliers’ profit attributable to CERN LHC procurement (sales net of costs) and the volume of all CERN contracts**²⁰.
2. We **apply the ratio as multiplier to the fraction of technologically intense portions of the FCC-ee related procurement**.

As a starting point for the estimation of the multiplier, **we build on previous results published by Castelnovo et al. (2018)**, which analyse a sample of LHC procurement contracts and estimate the net incremental effect on revenues and profitability for CERN suppliers after their first contract with CERN. The sample is obtained by extracting from the CERN LHC procurement database including contracts over the 1995-2008 period. 1 269

²⁰ The calculation of the profit excludes the direct sales to CERN. In other words, the multiplier considers only the turnover/profit that suppliers have generated in other markets thanks to CERN as a consequence of having been suppliers, therefore excluding the direct sales to CERN.

industrial suppliers from 34 countries which received at least one order above 10 000 CHF for the LHC construction²¹ were considered. For these firms, financial data on their revenues and profitability (EBIT = revenues net of losses, depreciation and amortisation but gross of interests and taxes) were collected from the ORBIS global database of companies. The final sample includes 351 supplier companies for which long time series of financial data are available both before and after the year of the first contract with CERN.

Table 6. Sample of LHC supplier companies used to determine the sales multiplier.

Initial LHC procurement database from CERN (Population)		Sample considered
1,269 suppliers from 34 countries Period 1995-2008 13,804 orders (> 10,000 CHF)	Financial data are available for a long period of time before and after becoming CERN supplier (source: ORBIS database)	351 (28%) suppliers from 18 countries Period: 1995 - 2008 Period of analysis (incl. financial data): 1991 - 2014 2,329 (17%) orders (> 10,000 CHF)

Source: Authors based on Castelnovo et al. (2018).

This sample includes mainly large firms, based in France, UK, Spain, Germany, and Italy. Most of them (58%) supplied goods that have a higher technological intensity and level of innovation²². Technology intense orders of the LHC concern mainly magnets, building work (incl. civil engineering), cryogenic technologies and low-temperature materials (e.g. superconducting materials, magnets and radiofrequency systems).

Using multivariate regression analysis, Castelnovo et al. (2018) found that:

- **becoming a LHC project supplier is associated with an average net increase in revenues of 45.6 million Euro (71 MCHF)²³ and a net increase in average profitability of 6 million Euro (9.3 MCHF)²⁴ for each firm.** This is the average net effect after correction of any other factors that could impact on revenues, such as company size, inflation dynamics, GDP cycle, pure time effects and geographic-country effects.
- **The procurement effect on revenues and profitability is higher for high-tech suppliers** than for low-tech ones: if only the sub-sample (n = 222) of high-tech suppliers is considered,²⁵ the net impact on revenues is 56.7 million euro and on profitability (EBIT) is 8.8 million euro (13.7 MCHF) per firm on average as shown in Column 3.

Table 7 shows the results of the regression analysis.

Table 7. Impact of LHC procurement on suppliers' revenues and EBIT.

	All sample (n=351)		Only hi-tech sample (n=222)	
	Yearly variation operating revenues (th EUR)	Yearly variation EBIT (th EUR)	Yearly variation operating revenues (th EUR)	Yearly variation EBIT (th EUR)
Factors influencing suppliers' revenues/EBIT	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
LHC procurement effect	45,596.1***	5,999.5***	56,770.6***	8,863.1**
Supplier Size				

²¹ Only orders above 10 thousand CHF were considered so as not to include the smaller off-the-shelf contracts to which no industrial spill overs is generally associated.

²² The classification of orders into high and low-tech follows Castelnovo et al (2018) and is based on a sample of 300 LHC orders exceeding CHF 10,000. These orders were classified with the help of experts at CERN according to a five-point scale 1) "very likely to be off-the-shelf products with low technological intensity"; 2) "off-the-shelf products with an average technological intensity"; 3) "mostly off-the-shelf products, usually high-tech and requiring detailed specifications"; 4) "high-tech products with a moderate to high specification activity intensity to customize a product for LHC"; 5) "products at the frontier of technology with an intensive customization work and codesign involving CERN staff." Notice that the term "product" also includes material treatments, consultancies, constructions, installations and other services.

²³ The standard deviation of the normal distribution is equal to 18.4 million Euro.

²⁴ The standard deviation of the normal distribution is equal to 2.3 million Euro.

²⁵ Firms that have more than 50% of their orders labelled as high-tech.

<i>Very large</i>	8,655.2***	295.0	11,833.7**	824.8
<i>Large</i>	-867.1	1,440.6	-4,178.2	1,924.0
<i>Medium</i>	-1,022.1	77.91	-2,333.4	213.1
<i>Small</i>	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Macro-economic factors:				
<i>Annual variation of Inflation</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>Annual variation of country GDP</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time factors (year-fixed affects)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Years*country	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	-30,830.7***	-2,531.8***	-18,338.2***	-2,605.3***
R-squared	0.085	0.114	0.132	0.147
N of observations	5799	5812	3703	3706

Source: Authors based on Castelnovo et al. (2018).

*Note: Panel fixed-effects regression; Period 1991 – 2014. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.*

Next, we divide the net economic effect of procurement (previously estimated by Castelnovo et al.) by the value of the procurement contracts. This calculation provides a value for the procurement multiplier. The analysis revealed that

- **1 Euro spent by for LHC procurement generates on average 15.3 Euro of additional revenues and 2 euro of additional profits for the supplier;**
- **1 Euro spent by on a *high-tech* procurement contract generates on average 20 Euro of additional revenues and 3.11 Euro of additional profits for the supplier.**

The steps taken to estimate these multipliers are presented in the following table.

Table 8. Workflow to determine LHC procurement multipliers.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reference suppliers: CERN LHC suppliers between 1995-2008 • Period of analysis (incl. financial data): 1991 - 2014 			
Item	Value	Formula/Source	
CERN LHC procurement effect on supplier's revenues (1 supplier)	EUR 45,596,100	Castelnovo et al (2018)	(A)
CERN LHC procurement effect on supplier's EBIT (1 supplier)	EUR 5,999,500	Castelnovo et al (2018)	(B)
CERN LHC hi-tech procurement effect on supplier's revenues (1 supplier)	EUR 56,770,600	Castelnovo et al (2018)	(C)
CERN LHC hi-tech procurement effect on supplier's EBIT (1 supplier)	EUR 8,863,100	Castelnovo et al (2018)	(D)
CERN LHC procurement effect on suppliers' revenues (all sample, n=351)	EUR 16,004,231,100	(A)*351	(E)
CERN LHC procurement effect on suppliers' EBIT (all sample, n=351)	EUR 2,105,824,500	(B)*351	(F)
CERN LHC procurement effect on suppliers' revenues (hi-tech sub-sample, n=222)	EUR 12,603,073,200	(C)*222	(G)
CERN LHC procurement effect on suppliers' EBIT (hi-tech sub-sample, n=222)	EUR 1,967,608,200	(D)*222	(H)
Value of CERN LHC procurement contracts (all sample, n=351)	EUR 1,045,640,979	CERN LHC procurement database	(I)
Value of CERN LHC hi-tech procurement contracts (hi-tech sub-sample, n=222)	EUR 616,195,793	CERN LHC procurement database	(J)
Revenues MULTIPLIER	15.31	(E)/(I)	(K)
Profitability (EBIT) MULTIPLIER	2.01	(F)/(I)	(L)

Revenues MULTIPLIER (hi-tech)	20.45	(G)/(J)	(M)
Profitability (EBIT) MULTIPLIER (hi-tech)	3.11	(H)/(J)	(N)

Source: Authors based on Castelnovo et al. (2018).

Profits are a more conservative proxy of economic performance than revenues, which explain why the profit/procurement ratio is lower. Also, the **profit/sales multiplier is comparable with the utility/sales multipliers previously used in the literature**, which defined the economic utility in terms of incremental revenues minus potential losses or costs (Schmied, 1977; Bianchi-Streit et al., 1984).²⁶

Considering that previous studies on the LEP programme revealed an average utility/sales multiplier of high-tech procurement of 3, the profit/sales multiplier computed for the LHC (3.11 for high-tech procurement) confirms the previous estimates.

For the estimation of the industrial spillover benefits of FCC-ee, **we assume that the LHC multiplier would also apply to FCC-ee procurement**. Taking the FCC-ee cost items listed in Section 3.4, their degree of high-tech intensity has been assigned in the following way:

- First, the share of investment costs that can be considered high-tech has been estimated;
- Then, the degree of technological intensity has been indicated on a scale from 1 (low) to 5 (high).

The specific attributions are presented in the following Table.

²⁶ Schmied, H. (1977), 'A study of economic utility resulting from CERN contracts,' IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management, EM-24(4),125–138.
Bianchi-Streit, M., R. Blackburne, R. Budde, H. Reitz, B. Sagnell, H. Schmied and B. Schorr (1984), 'Economic Utility Resulting from CERN Contracts: (Second Study),' CERN Paper, 84-14, Geneva.

Table 9. FCC-ee technological intensity levels and fractions for segments and subsystems.

System	Domain	High-tech share of the procurement [0-1]	Technological intensity level [1-5]	Technological intensity origin
Main ring magnet system	Accelerator	0.5	5	Design and interface engineering, testing, use of re-cycled materials
Main ring vacuum system	Accelerator	0.5	5	High performance and efficiency vacuum, surface treatments and additive manufacturing, material interface management, high precision and clean work, testing
Main ring power converters and cabling	Accelerator	0.3	3	Energy efficiency, battery systems, reliable DC grids, fast controls, safety relevant systems, interface and systems management, embedded computing and controls
Main ring beam transfer systems	Accelerator	0.5	4	Custom developments
Main ring beam diagnostics	Accelerator	0.8	5	Detectors, fine mechanics, electronics, software, embedded systems, data processing
Other main ring (controls, protection)	Accelerator	0.5	4	See above
Injector magnet system	Accelerator	0.5	5	See above
Injector vacuum system	Accelerator	0.5	5	See above
Injector power converts & cabling	Accelerator	0.3	3	See above
Injector beam transfer systems	Accelerator	0.5	4	See above
Injector beam diagnostics	Accelerator	0.8	5	See above
Other injector (controls, protection)	Accelerator	0.5	4	Systems engineering, design, software development, electronics
Main and top-up ring RF system (Z)	Accelerator	0.5	5	Superconductivity, thin films, novel manufacturing, interface designs, 3D integration, energy efficient power sources
Main and top-up ring RF system (W)	Accelerator	0.5	5	See above
Main and top-up ring RF system (H)	Accelerator	0.5	5	See above
Main and top-up ring RF system (ttbar)	Accelerator	0.5	5	See above
Cryogenics	Accelerator	0.4	3	Standard cryogenics, but very low temperature (1.2 K) with energy efficiency increasing systems and heat recovery
Injector w. e+/e-sources	Accelerator	0.5	5	Standard particle accelerator technology, but focus on reliability, efficiency, cost savings
Transfer lines	Accelerator	0.5	5	Custom developments
Adaptation of CERN machines	Accelerator	0.1	3	Custom developments, refurbishment
Electricity infrastructure	Infrastructure	0.1	3	Efficient high-power distribution, low loss energy transmission, reliability
Cooling and Ventilation	Infrastructure	0.3	3	Energy efficiency, heat recovery, novel heat dissipation systems, water management
Transport and Installation	Infrastructure	0.1	2	Autonomous or supported installation and transport, advanced vehicles and elevators, logistics simulations
Other technical infrastructures	Infrastructure	0.1	2	Custom developments
Detector 1	Experiment	0.8	5	Particle detectors, electronics, advanced materials, software
Detector 2	Experiment	0.8	5	See above
Civil engineering	CE	0.1	3	Project management, ICT support for

construction				construction and recycling activities, advanced subsurface construction and engineering, environmental friendly construction techniques, architectural and landscape integration works.
Operation developments	Operation	0.5	5	High tech developments during the operation phase to improve the performance, efficiency and create new functions. The fraction of operation costs to which this applies per year will be determined when the operation costs are known.

We quantify the industrial spillover impact of procurement as follows:

- We take the share of FCC-ee construction costs that are considered to cater a certain share of technological intensity;
- For investments with a technological intensity level of 4 and 5, the multiplier for the high-tech orders is applied. The profit /sales multiplier will be used as a preferred option.
- For investments with a technological intensity level of 2 and 3, the average profit/sales multiplier is applied.
- A multiplier value of 1 (no multiplier) is applied to FCC-ee construction costs with a low technological intensity level (off-the shelf products or standard services)²⁷.

The estimation may be refined in two ways:

- By considering a probability distribution of the multiplier;
- By also considering the territorial benefits of procurement that expands beyond the supplier firms (see Section 5.1). The methodology may therefore be updated once the results of these research activities are obtained.
- By considering spillover effects during the operation phase for the supply of specific services that remain to be compiled.

²⁷ It means that a multiplier of 1 is implicitly assumed.

4.4. IMPACT PATHWAY 4: DATA, INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES

4.4.1. Definition of the benefit

The development of ICT tools and the generation of widely available data not limited to scientific results (e.g. engineering test data, operation monitoring, system tests, etc.) are essential outputs of research infrastructures. Collectively, the LHC experiments produce about 15 petabytes of raw scientific data each year that is analysed using a worldwide distributed data processing environment, the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG). In 2017, the permanently stored data exceeded 200 petabytes. The WLCG distributes today data from CERN to 11 major computing centres in Europe, North America and Asia. From there, it is sent to 170 centres in 42 countries. While raw, pre-processed and annotated data is first made available to the members of the scientific collaborations of the LHC experiments, a subset of the annotated data and simplified data suitable for self-programmed analysis software is also made available with a delay to researchers who are not members of the collaborations, schools and interested people via open access data infrastructures.

To put in place a global data sharing- and processing infrastructure has led to the creation of numerous, openly accessible software packages, which are also used in environments outside high-energy physics. They range from scalable data storage and distribution middleware over data data analysis and visualization to data management and workflow systems.

Also, at the periphery openly accessible software has been developed with value that extends beyond the scientific collaborations. Examples include innovative Cloud computing services (e.g. Helix Nebula Science Cloud²⁸ serving five scientific research domains), meeting and event management software (e.g. Indico) and information access software (e.g. Zenodo).

The value of ICT technologies and open data produced by a research infrastructure is an understudied topic in the socio-economic impact literature. A few previous studies have analysed the socio-economic impacts of the ROOT and GEANT4, two software packages that relate to the LHC construction and operation that are today used by individuals and organisations beyond the high energy physics community (Florio, Forte, Sirtori, 2016; Catalano et al., 2019). The analysis conducted under this impact pathway will expand on previous case studies and consider a wider set of software and IT systems.

4.4.2. Assumptions

Since it is virtually impossible to forecast the ICT developments and innovations that the FCC-ee will induce due to the highly dynamic nature and fast technological progress in this domain, this impact pathway will adopt a backward-looking perspective. By considering software with different characteristics, different users and benefits, this impact pathway will describe the conditions for the benefit generation and the different channels through which a research infrastructure can generate benefits as spillovers from its ICT-related activities.

The socio-economic impacts of open data and software created for CERN's scientific programme will be assessed through specific case studies, that will complement the impact assessment already carried out by previous studies of two software developed by CERN for the operation of LHC: GEANT4 and ROOT (see Box 2 below).

Box 2. Methods used to assess the socio-economic benefits of GEANT4 and ROOT

Both ROOT and GEANT4 were developed by CERN in relation to LHC computing needs. ROOT is an open-source framework for data processing to analyse big quantity of data and perform simulations. On the basis of yearly download statistics of the software code, non-CERN ROOT users outside the high-energy physics community are estimated to be about 25 000 worldwide in 2013, in addition to about 10 000 HEP users. The market prices of different comparable commercial software (from R to Oracle Advanced Analytics) have been analysed to estimate the "avoided costs" for ROOT's users, thanks to the free and open software developed by HEP community. The socio-economic value was then validated also through a direct survey to ROOT's users.

²⁸ https://www.hnscicloud.eu/sites/default/files/files/HNSC_BookletA5_November2018_21081123_web.pdf

GEANT4 is an open software for data simulation. Beyond CERN and the HEP community, it is used by about other fifty research centres, space agencies and firms, as well as hospitals (e.g for simulating damages in DNA). The socio-economic value of this software is estimated based on the cost undertaken to develop it (number of hours and average salary of software developers).

Source: Authors based on Florio, Forte, Sirtori (2016) and Catalano et al. (2019).

The following three cases will be considered to develop forecast models of typical examples of systems:

- **Zenodo** is a digital library system for scientific products encompassing open data, software and publications. It is a so called “catch-all” repository. Zenodo has been set up at CERN based on their Invenio software. Zenodo was launched in 2013 by the EC to support their nascent Open Data policy by providing a repository for EC funded research. Zenodo is hosted and operated by CERN. It serves as an example of a typical information system platform that large-scale research programmes require.
- **Protonmail** is a secure e-mail system developed by scientists from CERN and MIT. This technological spillover product is today developed, operated and marketed by a privately owned company in Geneva, Switzerland. It serves as an example for a typical high-tech spinoff and startup.
- **Indico** is a Web service to manage events of all kinds and sizes. This includes personal meetings as well as working group meetings, workshops and conferences as well as training events and visits. The system includes planning, agenda, invitations, registrations, payments, document archive (presentations and materials), minutes, integration with video conferencing tools and in-room video conferencing systems, attendant feedback and an ever-growing portfolio of additional functions that are added on an as-needed basis. The system is developed and operated by CERN for a world-wide user community of more than 15 000 people. This tool is used by other organisations such as the United Nations headquarter and research institutions world-wide. It serves as a typical example for a tool that global collaborations require.

In general, the impact analysis approach will be based on the following steps:

- **Identify and quantify the users:** to this end, statistics on software downloads and registrations will be obtained from the service providers; data for Zenodo and Indico users are available from the developers at CERN;
- **Understand how the software is used and what advantages users gain,** if possible, compared to similar alternative solutions: this information will be collected through surveys launched to the communities of users, but also potential users;
- **Estimate the socio-economic value** of benefits generated by each software for the non-CERN community of users. This value can be derived from willingness-to-pay estimates, cost of production (by quantifying and valuing the financial and human resources employed for the development of the software), or the commercial price applied by similar software available on the market. For Zenodo, a possible option includes looking at similar commercial open data environments, such as the one developed by Springer Nature, and at the price paid by its users as a proxy of the economic value attached by people to this kind of tools.

4.5. IMPACT PATHWAY 5: CULTURAL BENEFITS

4.5.1. Definition of the benefit

Creating an interest in science in all citizens is among the missions of any research infrastructure. To this end organisations participating in the FCC-ee project have launched and will further develop activities to attract the interest of lay people, for instance through the organisation of permanent and temporary exhibitions, open days and guided tours. Social media, broadcasting, news and reports in press, websites are also used to disseminate news and facts about the activities carried out. The Science Gateway²⁹, a new visitor centre at CERN to be inaugurated in 2022, confirms the aim to increase scientific dissemination.

The ultimate beneficiaries of outreach activities are visitors to the infrastructure, both in-person and virtual visitors. Previous studies have valued the cultural benefits for visitors by estimating the willingness-to-pay (WTP) for a visit³⁰. The most common way to estimate the WTP is through the travel cost method (see box below)³¹. For virtual visitors, the socio-economic benefits can be estimated by valuing the estimated time spent on the social media and other on-line communication channels.

Box 3. The travel cost method

The travel cost method (TCM) was suggested by Hotelling (1947) and developed by Clawson and Knetsch (1966) to assess the value of environmental resources and recreational sites³². The TCM has also gained popularity in cultural economics, particularly regarding cultural heritage³³. The method attempts to place a value on a non-market good by drawing inferences from expenditures incurred to ‘consume’ it, including the cost of the trip (e.g., fuel, train, or airplane ticket), the opportunity cost of time spent travelling, entry fees, on-site expenditures, and accommodation costs.

In particular, two types of TCMs exist: the ‘individual demand approach’ and the more common ‘zone of origin approach’ (Anex, 1995). The latter is the simplest and least expensive approach and is applied by collecting information on the number of visits to the site from different distances. This information is used to construct the demand function and to estimate the economic benefits for the recreational services of the site. Instead, the individual demand approach uses survey data from individual visitors in the statistical analysis rather than data from each zone.

Although widely adopted, the TCM is affected by a major limitation that need to be addressed. The limitation relates to the apportionment issue arising whenever it is reasonable to assume that a trip is made for different reasons (a multi-purpose trip). Disentangling the willingness to pay of visitors for a given infrastructure when more than one attraction is located in the same site or in the same area could be arduous.

4.5.2. Assumptions

A first attempt of estimating the monetary value of the cultural impacts that can be associated to the LHC programme was carried out by Florio, Forte and Sirtori (2016) in the framework of a cost-benefit analysis of the LHC. Specifically, the following groups of beneficiaries were considered: (a) onsite CERN visitors; (b) visitors to CERN travelling exhibitions; (c) people reached by media reporting LHC-related news; (d) visitors to CERN and Collaborations websites; (e) users of LHC-related social media (YouTube; Twitter; Facebook; Google+); (f) participants in two volunteer computing programs. It was found that generated benefits amount to around 2.1 billion Euro (not discounted, 2013 prices), thus contributing to around 12% of the total benefits of the infrastructure.

An update of the estimations was carried out by Bastianin and Florio in 2018 in the framework of the cost-benefit analysis of the High Luminosity upgrade of the Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC), assessing its

²⁹ <https://sciencegateway.cern/home>

³⁰ See, for instance, Clawson and Knetsch (1966); Caulkins et al. (1986); Cuccia and Signorello (2000); and Bedate et al. (2004).

³¹ See for instance, Pearce (1993); Loomis and Walsh (1997); and Mendes and Proença (2005).

³² For a review, see, for instance, Garrod and Willis (1991); Hanley and Barbier (2009); and Tietenberg and Lewis (2008).

³³ See, for instance, Alberini and Longo (2005); Bedate et al. (2004).

economic costs and benefits up to 2038. It was found that benefits stemming from outreach activities represent 13% of total benefits mostly coming from on-site visitors (57%).

An investigation carried out by Crespo Garrido and Catalano (2018) has confirmed the value of cultural benefits to the general public provided by Florio et al (2016) and Bastianin and Florio (2018). More recently, Crespo Garrido (2020) focused on virtual visitors of CERN outreach activities, such as YouTube, social media (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and LinkedIn) and websites. Also, she reports results of a survey carried out to on-site visitors of the four LHC experiments. This work resulted in the creation of a spending distribution for on-site visitors that will be considered in this study to forecast the effects of the on-site visitors to the FCC-ee research infrastructure.

4.5.2.1. On-site visitors

To estimate the socio-economic cultural impacts for on-site visitors, the following steps are taken:

(i) Estimating the number of visitors

Preliminary estimates of future on-site visitors have been made. They distinguish between three types of visitors: **(i) CERN total visitors, (ii) visitors to experiments and (iii) open day visitors**. The number of visitors are forecast for both the scenarios with and without the FCC-ee.

It is worth clarifying that the total number of visitors to CERN per year refers to persons that visit any or a combination of the CERN visit points, such as e.g. microcosm exhibition, proton-synchrotron, LEIR, the globe, one of the LHC experiments, magnet assembly facilities, SCool lab and other highlights. The visitors to LHC experiments may either be part of an official registered visit (accounted in the total number of CERN visitors), or part of a dedicated group for the experiment only or individuals that visit the experiment only. Therefore, we consider the sum of these two figures in the estimation of this benefit. Additional visitors are expected during open days which are foreseen every 5 to 7 years.

Figure 7. Expected evolution of on-site visitors over the period 2030-2057 for FCC-ee and for the CFS.

Note: In both scenarios, the number of visitors to experiment refers to LHC experiments visitors until 2041. From 2042 onward, the figure – in the scenario with FCC-ee refers to visitors to ATLAS, PA and PG.

Estimates presented above rely on the following general assumptions:

- The total number of CERN visitors will increase up to 300 000 individuals per year after 2042 (extended maximum capacity with the creation of the Science Gateway) in the scenario with FCC-ee while it will decrease to 140 000 people after 2042 in the scenario without FCC-ee. For the scenario without FCC-ee, the assumption is based on the impossibility to visit LHC experiment sites some time after the end of the HL-LHC programme. In addition, an overall decreasing demand is expected. This assumption can, however, be relaxed and assumed that, instead, visits will continue for some years, taking advantage of the machine’s inactivity. After some time, the number of visitors will start declining, due to the loss of interest in the without-the-project scenario.
- The four LHC experiments – ATLAS, CMS, LHCb and ALICE - will operate until approximately 2040 in both scenarios. In particular, the four experiments will remain open for visit during the FCC-ee construction phase and possibly also during the FCC-ee operation phase. That leads to an increase of the visitor count in the FCC-ee scenario. After 2041, only ATLAS that is close to the new CERN Science Gateway will be converted into a permanent surface and underground visit facility. In the

scenario without FCC-ee, LHC experiments will not remain open for visit. As above, this assumption can be relaxed, assuming that underground visits to the LHC experiments will continue for some limited time.

- In the FCC-ee project scenario, visits will be allowed to the two experiment sites (PA close to CERN and PG on the opposite site) and the tunnel, both during the construction and operation phases (maintenance periods will permit access, experiments can be designed with visiting possibilities in mind, FCC-ee represents less health and safety hazards than the LHC and therefore visit possibilities are larger).
- Open days visitors will amount to 75 000 people per event in the scenario with FCC-ee while they will decrease up to 50 000 people in the scenario without (after 2041) due to the lack of a major attraction and motivation for visit.
- Correction factors will be used to calculate the total number of visitors and avoid double-counting the individuals that visit both CERN exhibitions and the experiments' sites (multi-purpose visits).

Table 10. Estimations of on-site visitors (with and without scenario): preliminary assumptions

Visitors	Scenario with FCC-ee	Scenario without FCC-ee
CERN visitors (Microcosm exhibition, proton-synchrotron, LEIR, the globe, magnet assembly facilities, SCool lab and other highlights)	Increasing up to 300 000 (after 2042)* Estimated total number (2030-2057): 7.8 million visitors	Decreasing to 140 000 (after 2042) Estimated total number (2030-2057): 5.3 million visitors
Non-operational LHC experiment sites (ATLAS, CMS, LHCb, ALICE)	All 4 LHC experiments until 2041** Only ATLAS after 2041** Estimated total number (2030-2057): 2.4 million visitors	All 4 LHC experiments until 2041** No experiments will remain after 2041** Estimated total number (2030-2057): 0.9 million visitors
FCC experiment sites (PA and PG) + Tunnel	During the construction and implementation phase Estimated total number (2030-2057): 2.4 million visitors	Not foreseen Estimated total number (2030-2057): 0
Open Days	Every 5 years (75 000) Estimated total number (2030-2057): 450 thousand visitors	Every 5 years but decreasing after 2041 (to 50 000) Estimated total number (2030-2057): 375 thousand visitors

*Note: *with the creation of Science Gateway. **2 years after the end of HL-LHC operation.*

More details on the assumptions underlying the estimation for total number of visitors, the number of visitors to the LHC experiments, PA and PG experimental sites as well as the subsurface structures are summarised in what follows.

- **CERN total visitors:** To estimate the evolution of the total visitors with and without FCC-ee, the existing information on visitors at CERN in the years from 2013 to 2019 was used as a basis. The current number of about 150 000 persons per year represents an upper limit of visitors that CERN can currently manage per year. The creation of the new visitor centre “Science Gateway” is expected to increase the capacity to about 300 000 people per year. This value corresponds to the number of visit requests received by the CERN central visit service in 2019. Under these assumptions, **the total number of visitors expected over the project time horizon (2030-2057) is 7.8 million.**
- **Visits to non-operational LHC experiment sites:** It will be possible to continue visiting the main LHC experiments during the construction period of the FCC-ee and possibly also beyond. We assume that only ATLAS remains as a permanent exhibit site, since it is next to the Science Gateway and therefore easier to manage than the other sites. The assumption is that visits are possible on 6 days during the week and over a period of 45 weeks (45 x 6 = ca. 280 visit days). During these periods, the LHC accelerator can also be visited. Under these assumptions, the total number of visitors to non-operational experiments over the project time horizon (2030-2057) is around 2.4 million.

- **PA and PG experiments: Experiments at the FCC-ee – PA and PG - will be designed and constructed having in mind the goal of allowing visits during the construction and operation phases.** Site security aspects are expected to limit the total concurrent number of people on site and underground and the total number of people per day. Some assumptions are set by relying on the existing historical data from CERN and the LHC experiments (Table 12).
- **FCC-ee tunnel: It will be possible to visit the FCC-ee tunnel.** It is assumed that it will be possible to visit the FCC-ee tunnel during 180 days. It is expected that 2.4 million people will visit the FCC-ee experiments and the tunnel between 2030 and 2057.

Figure 8. Evolution of centrally registered visitors to CERN per year: historical data, 2013-2019

Note: 2020 is excluded since the COVID-19 pandemic stopped visits in this year. 2019 must not be looked at as an ordinary year: in this year, CERN organized the Open Days, which attracted more than 80 000 additional individuals. Such events are foreseen every 5 to 7 years. These additional visitors are not accounted in the annual visitor statistics of the central visit service.

Table 11. Estimations of visitors to non-operational LHC experiment sites: underlying assumptions.

	Visitors/year	Days	Daily
ATLAS + LHC	50,400	280	170
CMS + LHC	47,600	280	180
ALICE + LHC	15,400	280	55
LHCb + LHC	15,400	280	55

Table 12. Estimations of PA and PG experiment visitors: underlying assumptions.

Characteristic	Value
Maximum size of a guided tour group	12
Tour duration	2 hours
Daily tour slots (4)	09h00-11h00 11h00-13h00 14h00-16h00 16h00-18h00
Maximum number of parallel groups	2 (one on surface, 1 underground)
Maximum number of visitors per day	4 groups of 48 people (24 surface + 24 underground) = 192 persons
Average number of visitors per day	180
Number of visit days	Fri, Sat, Sun, Mon, Tue, Wed = 6 days
Number of visit days / year	180
Average number of visitors per year per experiment	180 days x 150 people = 18'000

Table 13. Estimations of tunnel visitors: underlying assumptions.

Characteristic	Value
----------------	-------

Maximum size of a guided tour group	12
Tour duration	1.5 hours
Daily tour slots (5)	09h00-10h30, 10h30-12h00, 13h00-14h30, 14h30-16h00, 16h00-17h30
Maximum number of parallel groups	2 (tunnel visitor centre and tunnel visit)
Maximum number of visitors per day	5 groups of 24 people (12 surface + 12 tunnel) = 120 persons
Average number of visitors per day	150 estimated
Number of visit days	Fri, Sat, Sun, Mon, Tue, Wed = 6 days
Number of visit days / year	180
Average number of visitors per year per experiment	180 days x 150 people = 27'000, rounded to 30'000 people with additional VIP visits.

(ii) Estimating the willingness to pay

The travel cost method will be used to estimate the WTP of on-site visitors. Data is available from Crespo Garrido, I. D. R. (2020), which calculated the spending incurred by visitors to visit CERN by following the TCM individual demand approach. The results are based on a survey to 900 visitors (both groups and individual) carried out between June 2018 and May 2019. The estimate distinguishes two scenarios: (i) groups for which CERN is the main travelling purpose; (ii) individuals who visit CERN as a consequence of having travelled to the area for other reasons. In both scenarios, the estimated expenditure takes into account the cost for transport, food, accommodation, time to visit CERN exhibitions and souvenirs. When statistically analysing the results of the spending produced by the onsite visitors, a Kernel distribution has been found to fit well the actual data, as illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Spending distribution of visitors during different seasons.

Source: Crespo Garrido (2020).

Note: the survey was carried out between June 2018 and May 2019. It was structured in two rounds to cover two seasons of the year: 1st round goes from June to September 2018; the second round goes from October 2018 to May 2019.

More details on the average spending per country and the assumptions to estimate the continuous distribution are reported by Crespo Garrido (2020). We will consider those results and fine-tune them to estimate the future economic impact for visitors.

4.5.2.2. Virtual visitors

(i) Forecasting the number of virtual visitors

To forecast the number of virtual visitors, the following actions are needed:

1. distinguish among the possible channels used by people (social media, website, television, and radio);
2. use proper techniques to estimate the number of virtual visitors per type of communication channel, such as by using the number of ‘tweets’ and followers in Twitter, posts or pages in Facebook, subscribers of the YouTube dedicated channel or number of views of a video, estimated number of people watching an event on television, number of blog conversations, volume of web traffic,

registrations on the official website. When analysing the impact of social media, it is important to consider the number of “re-postings” of original posts, since the fundamental working principle of these media is based on the concept of spreading and amplifying news rapidly by echoing.

(ii) Estimating the benefit for virtual visitors

A broadly used method to attach a monetary value to non-market goods is contingent valuation, which consists of asking people to state the maximum amount they would be willing to pay to obtain a good or would accept as compensation to give away a good, contingent on a given scenario. However, empirical studies show that when consumers are accustomed to receiving an online service or content for free, their willingness to pay is very low or nil (see, for instance, Chyi, 2005). We argue that - as a direct extension of the travel cost method - the marginal cost of accessing and using the media can be used to estimate benefits from this outreach activity. Considering that most web and social media resources are free of charge, this is mostly given by the opportunity cost of users' time. Similarly, the social value of time spent in reading, listening, and viewing content related to RI outreach in the traditional media is a reasonable proxy for the benefits to users (net of any price paid by them). Information on the income of users and the time they spend on enjoying outreach activities by the RIs would indeed provide a reasonable estimation of these benefits, when the explicit WTP is not available through survey data. For the calculation purpose, what is needed is an estimation of the number of distinct virtual visitors, time spent by each of them on RI websites and related resources, and the marginal social value of time. The value of time to be used for the forecasts will consider established literature reporting on the value of time for leisure activities in different countries.

4.6. IMPACT PATHWAY 6: THE PUBLIC GOOD VALUE OF KNOWLEDGE

4.6.1. Definition of the benefit

Fundamental physics research infrastructures such as LEP, the LHC and FCC-ee advance our knowledge about the nature and the inner workings of the Universe. This knowledge is a ‘public good’³⁴. The public good value impact associated with FCC-ee consists of evaluating the pure value of scientific research for knowledge increase regardless of any use that could be made out of it (which, as explained in section 2.1, cannot be fully predicted). A share of the population is willing to pay for such research just for the curiosity and satisfaction that more about the universe could be known as a result of this scientific activity. Differently from the other impact pathways, this benefit does not target any particular category of users of and active participants in the FCC-ee scientific programme. It is therefore not captured by other types of benefits included in the socio-economic impact model. As discussed by Florio and Sirtori (2016) and Florio et al. (2016), the social benefit of knowledge *per se*, as a public good, is measurable and can be proxied by the so-called concept of Willingness to Pay (WTP) (see Florio and Giffoni, 2020).³⁵

In 2018 and 2019, CERN and CSIL conducted two surveys in France and Switzerland to understand whether and to what extent citizens are willing to pay for particle physics research at CERN and, specifically, for a new future particle collider project that can follow the LHC/HL-LHC research programme. By interviewing a representative sample of 1 000 people in each country³⁶, the investigation has shown that **about 50% of French and Swiss citizens are willing to pay an amount of money to fund such research projects. The non-willingness to pay of the other half of the population is largely motivated by the lack of means (e.g. unemployment, limited availability of budget, illness) and not by a lack of interest or opposition.**

Specifically, in 2018, a survey to 1 000 adult citizens was launched in France with the goal of knowing whether the French population would be willing to pay for a new particle collider at CERN, and if yes, how much. The survey revealed a positive WTP ranging from 4.5 CHF to 19 CHF per person per year (considering that one half of the population is willing to contribute and one half is not willing or has no means to contribute) on average³⁷. This was an encouraging result considering the fact that the actual amount each French citizen paid to CERN via taxation was 2.9 CHF in 2017.³⁸ Hence, the study has shown that, on average, each French citizen assigns the same value or more to the research with the LHC than what (s)he actually pays as a taxpayer (see Florio and Giffoni, 2020 for details). A very similar contingent valuation survey was launched in Switzerland in 2019, which returned an estimated mean WTP ranging from 42.1 CHF to 67.1 CHF with a mean of around 55 CHF per person compared to an actual tax contribution of 6.5 CHF per person in 2019 (Figure 10).³⁹

Beyond the quantification of the mean WTP in the two countries, the two experiments were also used to reveal the drivers of the citizens’ willingness to pay. The WTP for particle physics research at CERN is, first of all, a positively correlated function of the **income of citizens** (the higher the income, the higher the stated WTP) and a negatively correlated function of the **bid asked** (the higher the price asked to be paid to support such research, the lower the WTP)⁴⁰. Additional socio-economic characteristics that drive the respondents’ WTP are **the level of education** (tertiary educated persons are willing to pay more with respect to less educated people), **age** (on average the people with an age up to 35 years have a higher WTP than people above that age), **the family size** (respondents in families with more than three members are willing to pay less as compared to

³⁴ In public economics a public good is defined as being both non-excludable and non-rivalrous. As for knowledge, see Florio and Giffoni (2020); Stiglitz (1999); Archibugi and Filippetti (2015).

³⁵ The WTP is widely used also in Environmental Economics and Health Economics for instance when estimating the value of conservation of natural habitats (Johansson 1995, Pearce et al., 2006, Atkinson and Mourato, 2008). For studies in Health Economics see among others Smith (2003).

³⁶ The experiment in France involved a stratified sample of 1,000 people aged between 15 and 74, representative of the French population in terms of gender, age, education, yearly income, and region of residence. The experiment in Switzerland applied the same sampling strategy.

³⁷ The French WTP corresponds to EUR 4 to EUR 17 per person. The official exchange rate EUR-CHF in 2017 was 1.11.

³⁸ This corresponds to EUR 2.7 per person in 2017. The actual contribution per capita to CERN is calculated as the ratio between the total contribution to CERN and the population aged 15-74. The total contribution to CERN is from the CERN budget 2019.

³⁹ The details of the Swiss experiment are available in Giffoni and Florio (2021).

⁴⁰ This result is in line with most of the academic and grey literature on this topic (see Johnston et al., 2017), which shows that the demand of a (public) good increases as income increases and decreases as the price to be paid for those good increases.

those with less numerous families), and **scientific interests** (respondents with some interest in scientific subjects such as medicine, biology, astronomy, physics, and geology are willing to pay more).

On top of that, factors that positively influence the WTP for particle physics research are **personal beliefs and awareness of CERN’s existence**. For instance, **the experiments demonstrate that where a higher share of population knows what CERN is and what its research activity consists of, the WTP is higher**.

From a qualitative point of view, there are no relevant differences in the drivers of the WTP in the two countries. What differs is the level of the WTP. The higher WTP in Switzerland depends on higher per-capita income, but also the higher share of people being aware of CERN. When asked if they know CERN, 80% of Swiss respondents answered ‘yes’. 46% of the respondents answered ‘yes’ in France. Figure 10 summarises the results from the two experiments.

The following section focuses on the assumptions on how the findings in France and Switzerland can be transferred and generalised to other CERN Member States (MS), Associated Countries (AC) and potential further funding nations of FCC-ee to forecast the WTP.

Figure 10. Results of the survey experiments in France and in Switzerland

Source: Authors based on Florio and Giffoni (2020) and Giffoni and Florio (2021).

4.6.2. Assumptions

4.6.2.1. Methods to estimate the WTP

The WTP for any (public) good can be estimated in three possible ways:

- **The stated preference method** (Davis, 1963; Bishop, 1979): it consists in eliciting people’s WTP by directly asking them how much they would pay for a certain good or service. Carefully designed surveys are needed to elicit the WTP values reliably in a sample of the population. Then the results can be

transferred to the entire population. This method was applied to the experiments in France and Switzerland.

- **The revealed preference method** (Antoniou et al., 2007): it consists in determining the value people hold for a good by observing their purchases in the market that directly or indirectly relate to the good⁴¹. In our case, one possible way to proxy the revealed WTP for FCC-ee could be to consider the actual implicit contribution each person pays to CERN through taxation. However, there are clear limitations in assuming that the MS contribution to CERN reflects the real preferences of individuals for science.
- **The benefit transfer method** (European Commission, 2014): it consists in extrapolating the results of existing surveys and studies, and transfer them to different populations and contexts, after proper adjustments. This method can be less expensive and time consuming than stated preferences and revealed preferences techniques. However, it can return less reliable results⁴² and ad-hoc efforts are needed to check their robustness.

Due to contingencies linked to the Covid-19 pandemic and difficulties to reach people through direct interviews, as well as the high costs of conducting contingent valuation surveys in many different countries, we estimate at this stage the WTP parameter to be used for FCC-ee via the **benefit transfer method** and rely on the results of the two previous surveys, in particular the French one. The estimated values will be fine-tuned and verified later, for instance with surveys in different countries as time and resources permit.

4.6.2.2. Application of French WTP model to other CERN MS and AC via the benefit transfer

We apply the benefit transfer method by considering the following model:

$$\text{Mean (WTP) in } MS_i = \text{Mean (WTP)}_{FR} \left(\frac{\bar{X}_{1MSi}}{\bar{X}_{1FR}} * \frac{\bar{X}_{2MSi}}{\bar{X}_{2FR}} * \dots * \frac{\bar{X}_{nMSi}}{\bar{X}_{nFR}} \right)$$

where the mean WTP in MS i is given by the mean WTP in France adjusted by the ratio between the mean value of the socio-economic variables (\bar{X}_n) such as per-capita income, level of education, etc. in that MS and the mean value in France. For France the term in parenthesis is equal to 1 and the formula just returns the mean WTP in France.⁴³

In order to implement the benefit transfer method, for each CERN MS, we collected secondary data on observable variables influencing the WTP: the per-capita income (GDP), share of people with tertiary education, share of people aged less than 35 and the share of people with a family with more 3 members. To capture the scientific interest in a given MS, we collected a set of proxies: the share of people employed in science and technology, the share of scientists and engineers, and the average science literacy rate in the country. **No secondary data are available to capture non-observable information such as personal knowledge of CERN (awareness) or personal beliefs about the importance of scientific research carried out at the laboratory in other CERN MS (Table 14). Accordingly, these variables are not used in the benefit transfer**

⁴¹ The “travel cost” method applied for the evaluation of the “Cultural effects” impact pathways is an example of revealed preference method.

⁴² For a discussion on this topic see European Commission (2014).

⁴³ The advantage of this approach (which is non-parametric) is that it provides a simple recalibration of the French WTP, without relying on the French model’s parameters (β_s) (see Florio and Giffoni, 2020). It is not theory-dependent and is fully driven by the data in the sense that there is no need to assume any underlying distribution or theoretical structure of the respondents’ preferences. However, it does not consider the importance of the “impact” (as measured by the marginal value of the regression coefficients) of each variable on the mean WTP given by the respective parameters: in the non-parametric model, all influencing variables contribute at readjusting the French mean WTP, with no one having a stronger or a weaker role than others. In principle, preferences of people about a certain good and their WTP (along with the exact probability distribution) is a private information, which is unknown to the researcher and need specific WTP questions or methods to be elicited. Accordingly, there are no universal reasons to be in favour of one method or another one and most of the recent studies on contingent valuation rely on both parametric and non-parametric approaches when estimating the WTP (see among others Borzykowski et al., 2018; Johnston et al., 2017; Loureiro et al., 2004). In order to gauge the hypothetical level of the WTP for a future particle collider at CERN in other CERN MS, we apply the benefit transfer method by considering non-parametric approaches, which in general return more conservative WTP estimates as compared to parametric ones.

method at least at this stage. An overview of the value of the collected variables referring to the year 2019 is provided in Annex 7.5.

Table 14. Secondary data used to estimate the WTP.

Primary data used in the field experiment in France	Secondary data (proxy) from desk research used in the “benefit transfer” estimation	Source (year)
Income (\bar{X}_1)	Per capita GDP ⁴⁴	Eurostat (2019; 2018; 2017)
Tertiary education (\bar{X}_2)	Share of population with tertiary education	Eurostat (2019; 2018; 2017)
Age (< 35) (\bar{X}_3)	Share of population aged less than 35	Eurostat (2019; 2018; 2017)
Family size (> 3 members) (\bar{X}_4)	Share of households with more than 3 members	Eurostat (2019; 2018; 2017)
Scientific interest (\bar{X}_5)	Share of population employed in Science and Technology	Eurostat (2019; 2018; 2017)
	Share of scientists and engineers in the population	
	Average literacy rate of 15 year-old students	OECD PISA* (2018)

*Note: * OECD Program for International Student Assessment*

We apply the model in the equation above to estimate the WTP for the following countries for which noteworthy taxpayer contributions are likely based on memberships in CERN’s scientific research programmes:

- All 23 **CERN member states**: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovak Republic, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.
- The following pre-state member state countries:
 - Cyprus
 - Estonia
 - Slovenia
- **CERN associated states**:
 - Croatia
 - Latvia
 - Lithuania
 - Pakistan
 - Turkey
 - Ukraine
- The following **selected CERN observer states**:
 - Japan
 - Russian Federation
 - USA

For the time being, India is not included in the list due to the relatively limited monetary contribution to CERN’s scientific research programmes, as compared to the size of the population. This list may still be revised, depending on data availability and further internal discussions on the most relevant countries to consider.

We have collected data for CERN Member States, pre-stage Member States, and Associated States for three different specifications of the model (see Table 15)⁴⁵:

⁴⁴ The average GDP per capita in the period 2017-2019, the 2019 GDP per capita growth and the average annual GDP per capita in the period 2017-2019 have been used as proxies of the Income. No relevant differences emerge when the level of GDP per capita in different years is considering; in contrast, some the WTP in some countries seems to be overestimated when the GDP growth is used. For instance, considering the period 2017-2019, Eastern European countries such as Lithuania, Estonia, and Poland recorded an average annual GDP growth rate of about 3.5% respectively as compared to the annual growth rate of 0.7% in Germany and Italy, and 1% in France to mention just a few historical CERN MS. These different GDP growth rates translate into higher WTP for the above Eastern countries which is not likely to be plausible.

⁴⁵ We also run other specifications by combining in many different ways the available variables. The results do not substantially differ from those ones presented in the Table, which remain the most relevant specifications.

- Specification 1 includes the income as the only variable and can be considered as a baseline specification. It considers the WTP as a function only of respondents' income.⁴⁶
- Specification 2 adds other socio-economic variables to the baseline specification. The education level, age, and the family size are jointly plugged into the same specification along with the income.
- Specification 3 further adds the scientific interest to specification 2.⁴⁷

Table 15. Estimated WTP in CERN MS and AC in 2019 (CHF 2019).

Parameters/variables Included in the model	Specification (1) (income-based)	Specification (2) (income, education level, age, family size)	Specification (3) (income, education level, age, family size, scientific interest)
Income	√	√	√
Tertiary education obtained		√	√
Age < 35 years		√	√
Family with > 3 members		√	√
Scientific interest (people in STEM)			√
<i>CERN Member States</i>			
Norway	8.39	13.20	18.69
Denmark	6.71	8.87	12.80
Sweden	6.03	8.54	12.85
Netherlands	5.62	6.03	8.96
Austria	5.49	5.23	6.23
Finland	5.32	8.38	11.70
Germany	5.07	5.55	7.64
Belgium	5.08	5.01	5.48
United Kingdom	4.55	5.03	6.51
Italy	3.70	1.44	1.17
Spain	3.27	2.22	1.78
Portugal	2.54	1.33	1.25
Czechia	2.51	1.26	1.36
Greece	2.15	1.08	0.69
Slovakia	2.02*	0.78*	0.62*
Hungary	1.82	1.11	1.04
Poland	1.71	0.86	0.84
Romania	1.34	0.39	0.26
Bulgaria	1.03	0.55	0.44
<i>Associate Member States in the pre-stage to Membership</i>			
Cyprus	3.13	2.89	2.78
Serbia	0.80	0.26	0.18
Slovenia	2.83	1.56	1.71
<i>Associate Member States</i>			
Lithuania	2.09	2.58	2.82
Turkey	1.03*	0.55*	0.44*

Note: All the variables are from Eurostat and refer to 2019. * 2017 values are considered, as some of the variables used were not available either for 2018 or for 2019 for that specific country. The Table does not report CERN MS or CERN Associate MS that are not covered by Eurostat such as Israel, Pakistan, India, Ukraine.

Based on the above calculation, we adopt the following WTP parameters in the socio-economic impact model of the FCC:

⁴⁶ From the economic theory perspective, this is the simplest specification and it is in line with the basic axioms of consumer utility according to which the demand of a good is a negative function of the price (which is not observed here) and a positive function of disposable income.

⁴⁷ The scientific interest in the country is proxied by the share of population employed in Science and Technology. Other proxies such as the share of scientists and engineers or the average science literacy scores of young students by the OECD PISA have been used. Results are not statistically different from Specification 3.

- For France and Switzerland, we use the WTP estimated through contingent valuation surveys (expressed in 2019 terms):
 - In France, it has a minimum of 4.5 CHF and a maximum of 18.96 CHF
 - In Switzerland, it has a minimum of 42.1 CHF and a maximum of 67.1 CHF;
- For all other CERN MS and AC, we select the minimum and the maximum WTP per person for each MS estimated through the benefit transfer method. Results are visualized in the Table below from the highest to the lowest WTP. The WTP is also compared to the actual per-capita contribution that each MS pays to CERN as taxes. Results are reported in 2019 CHF⁴⁸.

The selection of the maximum and minimum values permits to address the WTP uncertainty stemming from the lack of direct information on people's preferences in CERN MS and AC beyond France and Switzerland and reduce the risk of estimation mistakes. Moreover, having a minimum and maximum WTP values enable us to run a probabilistic Monte Carlo simulation, drawing from a uniform probability distribution function, with the minimum and the maximum WTP to be used as parameters. The resulting simulated WTP will be plugged into the FCC-ee socio-economic model.

Table 16. Minimum and maximum estimated WTP per person in a preliminary list of countries to be included in the analysis (values are in CHF, year 2019).

Country	MIN WTP per capita	MAX WTP per capita	Mean WTP per capita (simple average)	Actual contribution to CERN per capita
France	4.5	18.96	13	2.9
Switzerland	42.1	67.1	55	6.5
Norway	8.39	18.69	13.54	6.43
Denmark	6.71	12.8	9.75	4.22
Sweden	6.03	12.85	9.44	3.62
Netherlands	5.62	8.96	7.29	3.56
Finland	5.32	11.7	8.51	3.26
Austria	5.23	6.23	5.73	3.26
Germany	5.07	7.64	6.35	3.29
Belgium	5.01	5.48	5.24	3.23
United Kingdom	4.55	6.51	5.53	3.36
Spain	1.78	3.27	2.52	2.02
Czechia	1.26	2.51	1.88	1.21
Portugal	1.25	2.54	1.89	1.41
Italy	1.17	3.7	2.43	2.26
Hungary	1.04	1.82	1.43	0.83
Poland	0.84	1.71	1.27	0.99
Greece	0.69	2.15	1.42	1.36
Slovakia	0.62*	2.02*	1.32*	1.22
Bulgaria	0.44	1.03	0.73	0.57
Romania	0.26	1.34	0.8	0.73

⁴⁸ Results in 2019 CHF were obtained by using 2019 data and are expressed in 2019 prices. For the sake of comparability to the French experiment, the Team have carried out the same exercise considering the year 2017 as well, where results are based on 2017 data and are expressed in 2017 prices. To avoid confusion and excess of information, 2017 results are not provided in this document; however, they are available upon request to the CSIL Team. On top of that, the same exercise has been done by considering the Swiss model as benchmark instead of the French model. Estimated WTPs are even higher in that case. Results are available upon request to the CSIL Team as well.

Cyprus	2.78	3.13	2.95	1.36
Serbia	0.18	0.8	0.49	0.42
Slovenia	1.56	2.83	2.19	0.57
Lithuania	2.09	2.82	2.45	0.42
Turkey	0.44*	1.03*	0.73*	0.09

Source: Authors.

*Note: All the variables are from Eurostat and refers to 2019. *indicates 2017 values as some of the variables used was not available neither for 2018 nor for 2019 for that specific country. The actual contribution per capita to CERN is calculated as the ratio between the total contribution to CERN and the Population aged 15+. The total contribution to CERN is from the CERN budget 2019.*

As next steps, we plan to refine the WTP results from the benefit transfer method above by:

- Trying to estimate the **WTP for other countries** that are not MS or AC, but that still has an interest in the implementation of FCC-ee (see the list of countries previously mentioned).
- **Finding a proxy of the awareness of CERN in the population** (i.e. knowledge of what it is and what its research activity consists of), since this is an important driver of the WTP.
- **Launch surveys in different countries to validate the results.** Time and money permitting, direct consultations could be launched in additional countries such as Italy, Germany, and Spain. The consultation should mirror the contingent valuation experiments already performed in France and Switzerland and the design of the survey should take on board their specific socioeconomic context in those countries, such as the level of income, the bid to be asked, etc. Those additional surveys in other key MS will help us bring new evidence of people's preferences for particle physics research carried out at CERN. It is however acknowledged that the results of a survey launched now, after the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic, may not be comparable with the previous surveys. **The Covid-19 event may have changed the preferences of individuals in the long run.** For instance, some people may be willing to pay more for scientific research in general than before the Covid-19 period. At the same time, people may now have a higher preference for research in medical sciences than in physics.

5. REGIONAL AND TERRITORIAL BENEFITS

FCC-ee is expected to generate socio-economic impacts at global, regional (within certain perimeters of activities in countries worldwide) and territorial (in the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region and in the Geneva canton) levels. The global socio-economic impact analysis will be complemented by investigating the regional and territorial impacts of the project from different perspectives:

- On one hand, the way how FCC-ee related procurement activities generate benefits beyond the supplier companies and how they spread across territories will be investigated.
- On the other hand, possibilities for generating socio-economic benefits locally throughout all lifecycle phases will be explored and included in strategic guidelines for the project.

5.1. TERRITORIAL BENEFITS OF PROCUREMENT

This spatial analysis expands on industrial spillover benefits beyond the firms and sectors initially involved in the procurement activities⁴⁹. It makes a step forward by **looking at how benefits spread beyond the boundaries of the firm in the region/country in which the suppliers are located, and also across-regions.**

A preliminary investigation has been carried out by considering superconducting radio frequency (SRF) systems as one specific technology associated with the FCC-ee construction. The SRF technology has been selected as a case study, as it will be at the heart of the FCC-ee (Benedikt, 2020). Over 11 years, 341 cryomodules (containing 1 364 cavities consisting of 2 600 cells) will be produced by selected industrial suppliers. This will be the largest deployment of this technology to date. Moreover, some of the components of the SRF systems, such as cavities, are exclusively produced for particle accelerators. Therefore, focusing on cavities allows us to consider benefits that can be specifically attributed to this kind of research infrastructure.

To estimate this type of socio-economic benefits, we decided to focus on XFEL at DESY (Germany), the first project in which SRF cavities were mainly produced in industry and the largest deployment of this technology to date (Singer et al., 2016). We will also look at other accelerators in which SRF cavities were produced in industry such as the FRIB at MSU (USA), CEBAF at JLAB (USA).

The socio-economic impact beyond the boundaries of the supplier is likely to depend on three factors:

1. potential use outside fundamental scientific research (market landscape);
2. market size for it (within basic research);
3. specificities of the procurement and manufacturing processes (number of competing actors, characteristics of the supply chain, potential for subcontracting, etc.).

Scoping interviews with INFN, DESY, JLAB, CERN staff and three firms (Zanon Research & Innovation, Roark and AES) involved in the production of SRF cavities and insights from conference proceedings revealed that most of the direct socio-economic benefits from SRF technologies are likely to materialize within the firm's boundary. However, there could be other socio-economic benefits whose spatial distribution is not known a priori, i.e. not necessarily in the same region in which the supplier is located. Due to the high technological intensity of the SRF technology, the investment size, the expected close collaboration between industry and CERN and the involvement of a large number of highly skilled individuals, **SRF-related procurement activities could generate spatially distributed socio-economic benefits through multiple channels.** A non-exhaustive list of potential channels includes⁵⁰:

- **commercialization of products and techniques outside basic research** (Salter and Martin, 2001);
- **production of scientific products (publications) and innovation, including patents** (Salter and Martin, 2001);

⁴⁹ Castelnovo et al., 2018; Florio et al., 2018; Autio et al., 2004.

⁵⁰ Other channels could be: (i) the creation of new firms by scientists and engineers involved in procurement activities. Our interviewees were not aware of any former employees of firms or RIs involved in SRF cavities procurement setting up a company; (ii) the acquisition of suppliers by other companies (Salter and Martin, 2001). There are only two companies in the market able to produce cavities in large scale, making the acquisition a limited mechanism for knowledge diffusion. However, Zanon Research & Innovation was recently acquired.

- **mobility of scientists and engineers involved in the procurement activities** (at both RIs and firms) to other organizations thereby contributing to knowledge diffusion;
- **contribution to job creation and economic activities** in the regions where the companies are located on a more macro-economic level.

Our scoping study revealed that the **mobility of scientists and engineers involved in procurement activities and the contribution to the economic activities in the region in which the suppliers are located seem to be the most relevant channels**. The methodological plan for assessing the procurement spatial impacts will include a mix of methods, depending on the specific types of impacts/channels to be investigated. The research team is exploring different options, including:

- the application of a Regional Economic Modelling model to assess the impact triggered by the procurement contract and expanding on the regional economies;
- the collection of data on the movements of the research infrastructure and supplier's staff, to track their movements across regions and, possibly, sectors after their procurement experience with the research infrastructure;
- qualitative case studies.

The scope of research will focus on the SRF systems and cavities in particular, but possibly on other technologies as well.

5.2. TERRITORIAL BENEFITS IN THE HOST-STATES

The analysis of the territorial socio-economic impacts aims at identifying and evaluating the benefits in France and in Switzerland potentially generated by the FCC-ee during the entire lifecycle of the project, including the feasibility and the pre-construction studies, the construction phase and the operational phase. This analysis will be linked to the placement optimisation outcome, local resource, service and infrastructure needs and strategies for eco-design. **The scope of this task is to increase the acceptability of the project.**

The “*territorial boundary*” of the analysis is a spatial perimeter defined on two levels:

- A “territorial dimension” (the blue circle in Figure 11 below) spans the FCC perimeter. It mainly covers two metropolitan areas, Grand Genève and Grand Annecy, as well as a number of more rural centers, in particular on the French side. This “territorial area” includes the area where CERN infrastructures are located today and where specific benefits (e.g. tourism) are more likely to materialize in the future.
- A “regional dimension” (the entire area shown in Figure 11 below) is a wider area around the FCC-ee sites in both host-states. The socio-economic impact generated in this area, considering the presence of academic institutions, companies and existing infrastructures, will be explored.

Figure 11. Spatial perimeters with two levels for regional impact studies.

Source: Authors

The methodology for the territorial analysis follows the socio-economic impact model as described in Chapter 4. The territorial benefits analysis will be based on the six impact pathways from the socio-economic impact model, properly adjusted to reflect the focus of the territorial and regional aspects. More specifically, the methodology will be based on the following steps:

- 1. Identify direct territorial and regional benefits** arising from the activities during the construction and operation phases. The analysis will include the identification of the potential beneficiaries. The benefits will be classified as follows:
 - private sector (e.g. the economic activities with industries involved in the construction and operation of the FCC-ee infrastructure, short and long-term job creation, job creation and distribution of employment between the two host-countries);
 - potential impacts on the long-term evolution of the population, the education level, the employment/unemployment rate and the quality of life;
 - housing (e.g. different housing needs during construction and exploitation phases);
 - education and training including the creation of opportunities for apprentices, students and highly qualified personnel training, R&D opportunities with territorial academic partners, engagement of schools, contribution of knowledge increase about the territory and its natural environments for the population and for visitors;

- urbanistic development opportunities (e.g. the FCC-ee offers the opportunity of network improvements for energy, water and transport management and the establishment of public facilities);
 - cultural development opportunities (e.g. increasing of tourism activity in the host-states and mainly at the experiments sites in connection to existing or newly created leisure activities at regional level).
 - environmental aspects (e.g. reinforced environmental protection, creation of natural protection zones, habitats and contribution to the preserving of biodiversity).
2. **Estimating indirect benefits.** They will be classified similar to the direct ones and include:
- impacts on the private sector and population (e.g. the potential economic growth due to increased commercial activities, supply contracts, growing population and tourism);
 - education and societal improvements (e.g. increased education levels, improved job opportunities, less unemployment due to increased educational offers and economic activities);
 - increased economic activities due to improved and new infrastructures (e.g. high tech companies, improved life quality, increased tourism, additional public transport)
 - beneficial effects for the natural environment (e.g. increase of flora and fauna quantity and quality due to reinforced and enlarged nature protection).
3. **Identify potential beneficiaries.**
- The potential beneficiaries will be identified and described. They will be included in a stakeholder inventory in order to develop tailored engagement approaches.

One long-term goal is to develop a concept for the creation of a new science and research hub that is close to the main experiment site PG in the Grand Annecy district. It will leverage the presence of the CNRS-LAPP laboratory in Annecy and will foresee its potential evolution (see Box 4). This hub complements the existing sites to operate the research infrastructure efficiently in the Haute-Savoie department.

Box 4. Potential CERN infrastructures evolution in the French Haute-Savoie department.

FCC requires an evolution of infrastructures in the Haute-Savoie department (France):

- The technical and experiment sites require technical infrastructures along the FCC ring;
- A second hub in the vicinity of experiment site PG will help operating the FCC in the Haute-Savoie region efficiently.
- Geographically dispersed sites in the Haute-Savoie department need the establishment of partnerships with local suppliers and create opportunities for partnerships with the society for increasing innovation, culture, education, smart-working, training on site, ICT services sharing, public health and safety and potentially further items.

Figure 12. Territorial impacts of the FCC-ee international project.

6. REFERENCES

- Alberini, A. and Longo, A. (2005). 'The Value of Cultural Heritage Sites in Armenia: Evidence from a Travel Cost Method Study', Working Papers 2005.112, Fondazione Eni Enrico Mattei.
- Amaldi, U., Aslanides, E., Barate, R., Benvenuti, C., Bloch, P., Camporesi, T., & Dissertori, G. (2019). Charting the European Course to the High-Energy Frontier. arXiv preprint arXiv:1912.13466.
- Anex, R. (1995). 'A travel-cost method of evaluating household hazardous waste disposal services', *Journal of Environmental Management*, 45: 189-198.
- Antoniou, C., Matsoukis, E., & Roussi, P. (2007). A methodology for the estimation of value-of-time using state-of-the-art econometric models. *Journal of public transportation*, 10(3), 1.
- Arbetsgruppen för SamhällsEkonomiska Kalkyler (ASEK, 2020), Kapitel 20 English summary of ASEK recommendations, Guidelines.
- Australian Government (March 2020). Cost-benefit analysis: Guidance Note, https://www.pmc.gov.au/sites/default/files/publications/cost-benefit-analysis_0.pdf
- Bacchiocchi, E., and Montobbio, F. (2010). 'International knowledge diffusion and home-bias effect: Do USPTO and EPO patent citations tell the same story? ', *The Scandinavian Journal of Economics*, 112(3): 441-470.
- Bastianin and Florio (2018). Social Cost Benefit Analysis of HL-LHC. Cern report, CERN-ACC-2018-0014. Available here: <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2319300/files/CERN-ACC-2018-0014.pdf> Last access on 25.05.2020.
- Bastianin, A., Castelnovo, P., Florio, M., Giunta, A. (2021). Big science and innovation: gestation lag from procurement to patents for CERN suppliers. *J Technol Transf* (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-021-09854-5>
- Battistoni, G., Genco, M., Marsilio, M., Pancotti, C., Rossi, S., & Vignetti, S. (2016). Cost-benefit analysis of applied research infrastructure. Evidence from health care. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 112, 79-91.
- Bedate, A., Herrero, L. C. and Sanz, I. (2004). 'Economic Valuation of the Cultural Heritage: Application to Four Case Studies in Spain'. *Journal of Cultural Heritage*, 5: 101-111.
- Ben Porath, Y (1967). The Production of Human Capital Over the Life Cycle. *Journal of Political Economy* , 75, pp. 352-65.
- Benedikt, M. (2020). Future Circular Collider - European Strategy Update Documents. January.
- Bianchin, C., Giacomelli, P., Iconomidou-Fayard, L., Niedziela, J., and Sciascia, B. (2019). Study on the career trajectories of people with a working experience at CERN. CERN Yellow Reports: Monographs, CERN-2019-004. <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2689210/files/90-78-PB.pdf>
- Bianchi-Streit, M., R. Blackburne, R. Budde, H. Reitz, B. Sagnell, H. Schmied and B. Schorr (1984), 'Economic Utility Resulting from Cern Contracts: (Second Study),' CERN Paper, 84-14, Geneva.
- Bishop RC, Heberlein TA (1979). Measuring values of extramarket goods: are indirect measures biased?. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*. 1979; 61: 926-930 <https://doi.org/10.2307/3180348>
- Borzykowski N, Baranzini A, Maradan D (2018). Scope effects in contingent valuation: does the assumed statistical distribution of WTP matter? *Ecological Economics*, 144: 319-329 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.09.005>
- Cabral, N. and Rodrigues, N.C. (2019). The Future of Pension Plans in the EU Internal Market. Springer Nature, Switzerland, AG. Project funded by the European Commission. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-29497-7>
- Cahill, N. and Dr O'Connell, L. (2018). Cost-Benefit Analysis, Environment and Climate Change, NESC Secretariat Papers Paper No. 15.
- Camporesi, T. (2001). High-energy physics as a career springboard. *European Journal of Physics*, 22(2), 139-148.

- Camporessi, T., Catalano, G., Florio, M., and Giffoni, F. (2017). Experiential learning in high energy physics: a survey of students at the LHC. *European Journal of Physics*, 025703 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6404/aa5121>
- Campos, J., Serebrisky, T., & Suárez-Alemán, A. (2015). Time goes by: recent developments on the theory and practice of the discount rate. Washington, DC: Inter-American Development Bank.
- Carrazza, S., Ferrara, A., and Salini, S. (2016). Research infrastructures in the LHC era: A scientometric approach. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 112, pp. 121-133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2016.02.005>
- Cass, D., Optimum growth in an aggregative model of capital accumulation. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 1965. 32(3): p. 233-240
- Castelnovo, P., Florio, M., Forte, S., Rossi, L., & Sirtori, E. (2018). The economic impact of technological procurement for large-scale research infrastructures: Evidence from the Large Hadron Collider at CERN. *Research Policy*, 47(9), 1853-1867.
- Catalano, G., Carrazza, S., Castelnovo P., Florio, M. (2019) *Assessing the value of CERN's free and open source software: the case of ROOT*, internal technical report available upon request.
- Catalano G. and Pancotti C. (2021). The social discount rates: recent estimations in selected countries. CSIL working paper, forthcoming.
- Catalano, G., Giffoni, F., & Morretta, V. (2021). Human and social capital accumulation within research infrastructures: The case of CERN. *Annals of Public and Cooperative Economics*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apce.12317>
- Catalano, G., López, G. G., Sánchez, A., & Vignetti, S. (2021). From scientific experiments to innovation: Impact pathways of a Synchrotron Light Facility. *Annals of Public and Cooperative Economics*.
- Caulkins, P.P, Bishop, R.C., Bouwes, N.W. (1986). The travel cost model for lake recreation: a comparison of two methods for incorporating site quality and substitution effects, *American Journal of Agricultural Economics* 68 (2): 291–297.
- Clawson, M. and Knetsch, J.L. (1966). *Economics of outdoor recreation*, Johns Hopkins Press.
- CPB Netherlands Bureau for Economic Policy Analysis and PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency (2013) *General Guidance for Cost Benefit Analysis*, The Hague.
- Crespo Garrido, I. D. R. (2020) *Socio-economic impact at CERN: Social networks and onsite CERN visitors* (Doctoral dissertation, Rey Juan Carlos U., Madrid). <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2711506>
- Crespo Garrido, I. D.R., & Catalano, G. (2018). *Cultural Effects at CERN*. CERN-ACC-2018-0048. <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2649022>
- Cuccia, T. and Signorello, G.A. (2000). 'A contingent valuation study of willingness to pay for visiting a city of art: the case study of Noto', *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Cultural Economics*, Minneapolis, 28–31 May, 2000.
- Davis RK (1963). *The value of outdoor recreation: an economic study of the Maine woods*. Unpublished Ph. D. dissertation, Harvard University.
- Department of Public Expenditure and Reform (2019) *Public Spending Code. Central Technical References and Economic Appraisal Parameters*, <https://assets.gov.ie/20001/35c13bbd055a4a09961a4ec59c93c798.pdf> (accessed on May 18th 2021).
- Drupp, M. A., Freeman, M. C., Groom, B., & Nesje, F. (2018). Discounting disentangled. *American Economic Journal: Economic Policy*, 10(4), 109-34.
- Environmental Protection Agency (EPA 2013). *Technical Support Document:-Technical Update of the Social Cost of Carbon for Regulatory Impact Analysis-Under Executive Order 12866*. https://www.epa.gov/sites/production/files/2016-12/documents/scc_tsd_2010.pdf (accessed on March 29th 2021).
- Environmental Protection Agency (EPA 2018), *Regulatory Impact Analysis for the Proposed Reconsideration of the Oil and Natural Gas Sector Emission Standards for New, Reconstructed, and Modified Sources*, EPA-452/R-18-001 (Washington, D.C.: September 2018).

- ESF (2013). Research infrastructures in the European Research Area – A report by the ESF Member Organisation Forum on Research Infrastructures.
- ESFRI (2017). ESFRI Scripta Volume II. Long-Term Sustainability of Research Infrastructures. Report by the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures Long-Term Sustainability Working Group. Available at https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/u4/ESFRI_SCRIPTA_SINGLE_PAGE_19102017.pdf.
- ESFRI (2008). European Roadmap for Research Infrastructures – Roadmap 2008.
- ESFRI (2010). Strategy Report on Research Infrastructures – Roadmap 2010.
- Eurofound (2020) <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/topic/retirement> Last access on 29.05.2020
- European Commission (2010). Communication from the Commission Europe 2020 - A strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth, COM(2010) 2020.
- European Commission (2020). Duration of working life -statistics. Available here: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/pdfscache/57155.pdf>. Last access on 25.05.2020.
- European Commission, (2014). Guide to cost-benefit analysis of investment projects. Economic appraisal tool for Cohesion Policy, 2014-2020, Directorate for Regional Policy, authored by Sartori, D., Catalano, G., Genco, M., Pancotti, C., Sirtori, E., Vignetti, S., & Del Bo, C.
- Feller, I. (2013). Peer review and expert panels as techniques for evaluating the quality of academic research, in Link, A.N., Vonortas, N.S. (eds) Handbook on the theory and practice of program evaluation, Edward Elgar.
- Finnish Centre for Pensions (2020). <https://www.etk.fi/en/the-pension-system/international-comparison/retirement-ages/>. Last access on 25.05.2020.
- Florio, M, and Giffoni, F. (2020). ‘A contingent valuation experiment about future particle accelerators at CERN’, PLoS ONE, vol. 15(3): e0229885. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0229885>
- Florio, M., Giffoni, F., Giunta, A. and Sirtori, E. (2018). Big Science, Learning and Innovation: Evidence from CERN Procurement. Industrial and Corporate Change, Volume 27, Issue 5, 915–936.
- Florio, M., and Sirtori, E. (2016). Social benefits and costs of large scale research infrastructures. Technological Forecasting and Social Change, 112, pp.65-78.
- Florio, M., Forte, S. and Sirtori, E. (2016). Forecasting the socio-economic impact of the Large Hadron Collider: A cost–benefit analysis to 2025 and beyond. Technological Forecasting and Social Change, 112, pp. 38-53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2016.03.007>
- Florio, M., Forte, S., Pancotti, C., Sirtori, E., & Vignetti, S. (2016). Exploring Cost-Benefit Analysis of Research, Development and Innovation Infrastructures: An Evaluation Framework working paper 01/2016, CSIL Centre for Industrial Studies, Corso Monforte, 15, 20122 Milano MI, Italy (March, 2016). arXiv preprint arXiv:1603.03654.
- Florio, M. (2014). Applied Welfare Economics: cost-benefit analysis of projects and policies. Routledge, New York. ISBN: 978-0-415-85833-5
- Florio, M. and Sirtori, E. (2013). The Social Cost of Capital: Recent Estimates for the EU Countries. Centre for Industrial Studies Working Paper 03, Milan, Italy.
- Freeman, M., Groom, B., & Spackman, M. (2018). Social discount rates for cost–benefit analysis: a report for HM treasury, published on the HMT Green Book web page.
- Garrod, G. and Willis, K. (1991). Economic Valuation of the environment: methods and case studies, Massachusetts: Edgar Elgar.
- German Federal Environment Agency (UBA, 2012). Economic Valuation of Environmental Damage—Methodological Convention 2.0 for Estimates of Environmental Costs, report prepared by Schwermer, S. Berlin, Germany.
- Giffoni, F. and Vignetti, S., 2019, Assessing the Socioeconomic Impact of Research Infrastructures: A Systematic Review of Existing Approaches and the Role of Cost-Benefit Analysis, L’industria, Fascicolo 1, gennaio-marzo.

- Griniece, E., Angelis, J., Reid A, Vignetti, S., Catalano, J., Helman, A., Barberis Rami, M. (2020), Guidebook for socio-economic impact assessment of research infrastructures, https://ri-paths.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/D5.4_RI-PATHS_Guidebook.pdf
- Hanley, N. and Barbier, E.B. (2009) Pricing Nature: Cost-benefit Analysis and Environmental Policy, Edward Elgar, Cheltenham
- HM Treasury (2018), The Green Book: Central Government Guidance on Appraisal and Evaluation, Treasury Guidance, London.
- Hotelling, H. (1947). 'Letter to the National Park Service'. Reprinted in: An economic study of the monetary evaluation of recreation in the national parks. (1949). Washington, D.C.: U.S. National Park Service
- INOMICS (2018). INOMICS Salary Report (2018). Available at <https://inomics.com/sites/default/files/2018-05/INOMICS%20Salary%20Report%202018.pdf> Last access on 23.01.2020.
- Invitalia (2014). Guida all'analisi costi-benefici dei progetti d' investimento: Strumento di valutazione economica per la politica di coesione 2014-2020, <https://people.unica.it/elisabettastrazzera/files/2017/10/LineeGuidaACB.pdf>
- ITF (2015), Adapting Transport Policy to Climate Change: Carbon Valuation, Risk and Uncertainty, ITF Research Reports, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789282107928-en>.
- Jaffe, A., B., Trajtenberg, M., and Fogarty, M.S. (2000). Knowledge Spillovers and Patent Citations: Evidence from a Survey of Inventors. *American Economic Review*, 90 (2): 215-218.
- JASPERS (2015). Project preparation and CBA of RDI infrastructure project. Staff Working Papers, JASPERS Knowledge Economy and Energy Division.
- Johnston, R.J., Boyle, K.J., Adamowicz, W., Bennett, J., Brouwer, R., Cameron, T.A., Hanemann, W.M., Hanley, N., Ryan, M., Scarpa R., Tourangeau, R., and Vossler, C.A. (2017). 'Contemporary guidance for stated preference studies', *Journal of the Association of Environmental and Resource Economists*, vol. 4(2), pp. 319-405.
- Koopmans, T., On the concept of optimal economic growth, in *The econometric approach to development planning*. 1965, North-Holland Publishing Co: Amstredam. p. 225-287
- Lemieux, T. (2006). The "Mincer equation" thirty years after schooling, experience, and earnings. In Jacob Mincer a pioneer of modern labour economics edited by S. Grossbard (pp. 127-145). Springer, Boston, MA
- Loomis, J.B. and Walsh, R.G. (1997) *Recreation Economic Decisions: Comparing Benefits and Costs*, 2nd edition, Pennsylvania: Venture Publishing.
- Lopez, H. (2008). The social discount rate: estimates for nine Latin American countries. The World Bank.
- Loureiro, M. L., Loomis, J. B., and Nahuelhual, L. (2004). A comparison of a parametric and a non-parametric method to value a non-rejectable public good. *Journal of Forest Economics*, 10(2), 61-74.
- Martin, B.R. (1996). The use of multiple indicators in the assessment of basic research. *Scientometrics*, 36 (3), 343-362.
- Maurseth, P.B. and Verspagen, B. (2002), Knowledge Spillovers in Europe: A Patent Citations Analysis. *Scandinavian Journal of Economics*, 104: 531-545. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9442.00300>
- Mendes, I. and Proença, I. (2005) 'Estimating the recreation value of ecosystems by using a travel cost method approach', Working Paper 2005/08, Department of Economics at the School of Economics and Management (ISEG), Technical University of Lisbon.
- Mincer, J. (1974). *Schooling, Experience and Earnings*. Columbia University Press: New York.
- Moore, M. A., Boardman, A. E., & Vining, A. R. (2020). Social Discount Rates for Seventeen Latin American Countries: Theory and Parameter Estimation. *Public Finance Review*, 48(1), 43-71.
- Mouter, N. (2018). A critical assessment of discounting policies for transport Cost-Benefit Analysis in five European practices. *European Journal of Transport and Infrastructure Research*, 18(4).
- Netherlands Discount Rate Working Group (2015). Rapport Werkgroep Discontovoet 2015', https://pure.uva.nl/ws/files/2661329/167999_rapport_werkgroep_discontovoet_2015_bijlage_2_.pdf (accessed on March 29th 2021).

- New Zealand Government (2015). Guide to Social Cost Benefit Analysis, prepared by the Treasury, available at <https://www.treasury.govt.nz/publications/guide/guide-social-cost-benefit-analysis> (accessed on March 29th 2021).
- New Zealand Government (2020). Technical Note on Social Discount Rate, prepared by the Treasury, available at <https://www.treasury.govt.nz/information-and-services/state-sector-leadership/guidance/financial-reporting-policies-and-guidance/discount-rates> (accessed on March 29th 2021).
- Ni, J. (2017). Discount rate in project analysis. Département Développement Durable et Numérique, France Stratégie. Available https://www.strategie.gouv.fr/sites/strategie.gouv.fr/files/atoms/files/10_fs_discount_rate_in_project_analysis.pdf (accessed on March 29th 2021).
- NOU (2012) Cost-Benefit Analysis, Official Norwegian Reports, NOU 2012: 16.
- O’Callaghan, d. a. n. i. e. l., Prior, s., & Unit, i. (2018). Central Technical Appraisal Parameters: Discount Rate, Time Horizon, Shadow Price of Public Funds and Shadow Price of Labour. Staff Paper 2018 Available at <https://igees.gov.ie/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/Parameters-Paper-Final-Version.pdf> accessed on March 29th 2021).
- OECD (2008). Report on Roadmapping of Large Research Infrastructures, OECD Publishing, Paris.
- OECD (2019a) Pensions at a Glance 2019. OECD and G20 Indicators, OECD Publishing, Paris. See (<http://oe.cd/pag>). Last access on 15.06.2020
- OECD (2019b) Benchmarking Higher Education System Performance, Higher Education. OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/be5514d7-en>.
- OECD (2020). Ageing and Employment Policies - Statistics on average effective age of retirement. Available here: <https://www.oecd.org/els/emp/average-effective-age-of-retirement.htm> Last access on 25.05.2020.
- Office of Management and Budget – OMB (2003). Circular No. A-4, "Regulatory Analysis".
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, OECD (2018). Cost-benefit Analysis and the Environment: Further Developments and Policy Use. OECD Publishing.
- Pearce, D.W. (1993) Economic Values and the Natural World, London: Earthscan.
- Planning and Priorities Co-ordination Division (2013) Guidance Manual for Cost Benefit Analysis (CBAs) Appraisal in Malta.
- Pozzo, R., Maegaard, B., Melloni, A., & Woollard, M. (2019). Stay Tuned the Future: Impact of the Research Infrastructures for Social Sciences and Humanities. Olshki.
- Psacharopoulos, G. and Patrinos, H.A. (2018). Returns to investment in education: a decennial review of the global literature. Education Economics, 26 (5) <https://doi.org/10.1080/09645292.2018.1484426>
- Quinet, E. (2007). ‘Cost Benefit analysis of Transport Projects in France’, in Florio, M. (ed.) *Cost Benefit analysis and Incentives in Evaluation*, Cheltenham: Edward Elgar.
- Quinet, E. (2013). L’évaluation socioéconomique des investissements publics Tome 1 Rapport final. Commissariat Generale a la strategie et a la Prospective.
- Ramsey, F.P. (1928). A mathematical theory of saving, The Economic Journal, 38(152): 543–559.
- Research Council UK. (2010). Large Facilities Roadmap 2010
- Salter, A. J., & Martin, B. R. (2001). The economic benefits of publicly funded basic research: A critical review. Research Policy, 30(3), 509–532. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333\(00\)00091-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333(00)00091-3)
- Schmied, H. (1977), ‘A study of economic utility resulting from CERN contracts,’ IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management, EM-24(4),125–138.
- Singer, W., Brinkmann, A., Brinkmann, R., Iversen, J., Matheisen, A., Moeller, W. D., Navitski, A., Reschke, D., Schaffran, J., Sulimov, A., Walker, N., Weise, H., Michelato, P., Monaco, L., Pagani, C., & Wiencek, M. (2016). Production of superconducting 1.3-GHz cavities for the European X-ray Free Electron Laser. Physical Review Accelerators and Beams, 19(9), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.19.092001>

- Sirtori, E., Catalano, G., Giffoni, F., Pancotti, C., Caputo, A., and Florio., M. (2019). Impact of CERN procurement actions on industry: 28 illustrative success stories. CERN, Geneva. Available at <http://cds.cern.ch/record/2670056/files/>
- Smith, R.D. (2003). 'Construction of the contingent valuation market in health care: a critical assessment', *Health Economics*, vol. 12(8), pp. 609-628. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hec.755>
- Solow, R.M. (1956). A Contribution to the Theory of Economic Growth. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*. 70(1): p. 65-94.
- Song, J., Almeida, P., & Wu, G. (2003). Learning-by-Hiring: When Is Mobility More Likely to Facilitate Interfirm Knowledge Transfer? In *Management Science* (Vol. 49, Issue 4).
- StR-ESFRI (2019). Guidelines on cost estimation of research infrastructures, drafted by CSIL –Centre for Industrial Studies, available at https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/StR-ESFRI2_STUDY_RIs_COST_ESTIMATION.pdf
- Swan, T.W., Economic Growth and Capital Accumulation. *Economic Record*, 1956. 32(2): p. 334-361.
- Technopolis (2011). The role and added value of large-scale research facilities. Final Report.
- Tietenberg, T. and Lewis, L. (2009). *Environmental and Natural Resource Economics*, Pearson, Boston, MA
- Treasury Board Secretary (2007). Canadian Cost-Benefit Analysis Guide Regulatory Proposals, <https://www.tbs-sct.gc.ca/rtrap-parfa/analys/analys-eng.pdf> (accessed on March 29th 2021).
- Treasury Board Secretary (2020), New policy on Cost-Benefit Analysis available at <https://www.canada.ca/en/government/system/laws/developing-improving-federal-regulations/requirements-developing-managing-reviewing-regulations/guidelines-tools/policy-cost-benefit-analysis.html> (accessed on March 29th 2021).
- U.S. Department of Commerce, National Institute of Standards and Technology (2013), Energy price indices and discount factors for life-cycle cost analysis - 2013, <https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/ir/2013/NIST.IR.85-3273-28.pdf>.
- US General Accounting Office (2007). Best Practices for Estimating and Managing Program Costs, Washington, DC.
- Vignetti, S. (2021). Designing a Research Infrastructure with Impact in Mind. In *The Economics of Big Science* (pp. 79-84). Springer, Cham.
- Zellner, C. (2003). The economic effects of basic research: evidence for embodied knowledge transfer via scientists' migration. *Research Policy*, 32, 1881–1895. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333\(03\)00080-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333(03)00080-5)
- Zhuang, L., Liang, Z., Lin, T. and De Guzman, F. (2007). Theory and practice in the choice of social discount rate for cost benefit analysis: A survey, ERD Working Paper n° 94, Asian Development Bank.

7. ANNEXES

7.1. FCC-EE PROJECT PARTICIPANTS: TABLES

Table 17. People working in two experiments at CERN FCC-ee and in the worldwide collaboration.

#	Phase	Activity	Cal. Year	Scientists + Post docs	Doctorate Students	Engineers	Undergraduate Students	Technicians Administration	Totals two experiments
1	Design 1		2028	200	20	20	10	30	280
2	Design 2		2029	500	20	30	10	30	590
3	Design 3		2030	1,000	20	30	10	30	1,090
4	Design 4		2031	1,100	30	50	20	30	1,230
5	Design 5		2032	1,200	30	60	20	30	1,340
6	Design 6		2033	1,200	30	70	30	60	1,390
7	Construction 1		2034	1,200	50	100	40	100	1,490
8	Construction 2		2035	1,300	100	100	50	100	1,650
9	Construction 3		2036	1,300	200	100	60	140	1,800
10	Construction 4		2037	1,400	300	150	70	140	2,060
11	Construction 5		2038	1,400	400	160	70	140	2,170
12	Construction 6		2039	1,400	500	160	80	150	2,290
13	Commssioning		2040	1,600	600	160	90	160	2,610
14	Operation 1	Z pole year 1	2041	2,000	700	200	200	200	3,300
15	Operation 2	Z pole year 2	2042	2,200	900	220	200	200	3,720
16	Operation 3	Z pole year 3	2043	2,400	1,000	200	200	200	4,000
17	Operation 4	Z pole year 4	2044	2,600	1,100	200	200	200	4,300
18	Operation 5	WW year 1	2045	2,800	1,200	240	200	200	4,640
19	Operation 6	WW year 2	2046	3,000	1,300	280	200	240	5,020
20	Operation 7	HZ year 1	2047	3,300	1,400	320	200	240	5,460
21	Operation 8	HZ year 2	2048	3,500	1,600	400	400	240	6,140
22	Operation 9	HZ year 3	2049	3,700	1,700	500	800	240	6,940
23	Operation 10	Upgrade	2050	3,600	1,700	550	1,200	400	7,450
24	Operation 11	Top year 1	2051	3,800	1,800	600	1,600	400	8,200
25	Operation 12	Top year 2	2052	4,000	2,000	600	1,600	400	8,600
26	Operation 13	Top year 3	2053	4,200	2,100	600	1,600	400	8,900
27	Operation 14	Top year 4	2054	4,200	2,200	600	1,600	400	9,000
28	Operation 15	Top year 5	2055	4,200	2,200	600	1,000	400	8,400
29	Post Operation 1	Analysis 1	2056	4,200	2,200	400	400	280	7,480
30	Post Operation 2	Analysis 2	2057	4,200	2,200	200	100	240	6,940
Totals				72,700	29,600	7,900	12,260	6,020	128,480

Source: Authors.

Note: The rightmost column indicates the total number of persons for two experiments. The project starts with the first significant engagement of financial resources in 2028. For the purpose of socio-economic impact analysis, the project ends two years after the last data taking. This lead-out phase is dedicated to data analysis and scientific research.

Table 18. People working in the particle accelerator and infrastructure project, mainly at CERN.

#	Phase	Activity	Scientists +	Doctorate	Engineers	Undergrad	Technicians	Totals
			Post docs	Students		Students	Administration	
1	Design 1		600	20	15	50	100	785
2	Design 2		600	25	15	50	100	790
3	Design 3		700	30	15	50	200	995
4	Design 4		700	30	15	50	400	1,195
5	Design 5		700	50	50	100	500	1,400
6	Design 6		700	50	50	100	600	1,500
7	Construction 1		700	50	50	100	700	1,600
8	Construction 2		700	50	50	100	700	1,600
9	Construction 3		700	50	50	100	700	1,600
10	Construction 4		700	50	50	100	700	1,600
11	Construction 5		800	50	50	100	700	1,700
12	Construction 6		900	50	100	100	1,000	2,150
13	Commssioning		1,100	80	200	150	1,500	3,030
14	Operation 1	Z pole year 1	1,200	100	300	200	2,000	3,800
15	Operation 2	Z pole year 2	1,300	100	300	200	2,000	3,900
16	Operation 3	Z pole year 3	1,400	100	300	200	2,000	4,000
17	Operation 4	Z pole year 4	1,500	100	300	200	2,000	4,100
18	Operation 5	WW year 1	1,500	100	300	200	2,000	4,100
19	Operation 6	WW year 2	1,500	100	300	200	2,000	4,100
20	Operation 7	HZ year 1	1,500	100	300	200	2,000	4,100
21	Operation 8	HZ year 2	1,500	100	300	200	2,000	4,100
22	Operation 9	HZ year 3	1,500	100	300	200	2,000	4,100
23	Operation 10	Upgrade	1,500	100	300	200	2,000	4,100
24	Operation 11	Top year 1	1,500	100	300	200	2,000	4,100
25	Operation 12	Top year 2	1,500	100	300	200	2,000	4,100
26	Operation 13	Top year 3	1,500	100	300	200	2,000	4,100
27	Operation 14	Top year 4	1,500	100	300	200	2,000	4,100
28	Operation 15	Top year 5	1,500	100	300	200	2,000	4,100
29	Post Operation 1	Analysis 1	1,300	20	300	20	2,000	3,640
30	Post Operation 2	Analysis 2	1,000	15	300	20	2,000	3,335
Totals			33,800	2,120	5,810	4,190	41,900	87,820

Source: Authors.

Table 19. People working in the particle accelerator and infrastructure project, mainly at CERN.

#	Phase	Activity	Cal.	Scientists +	Doctorate		Undergraduate	Technicians	Totals
			Year	Post docs	Students	Engineers	Students	Administration	FCC-ee scientific programme
1	Design 1		2028	800	40	35	60	130	1,065
2	Design 2		2029	1,100	45	45	60	130	1,380
3	Design 3		2030	1,700	50	45	60	230	2,085
4	Design 4		2031	1,800	60	65	70	430	2,425
5	Design 5		2032	1,900	80	110	120	530	2,740
6	Design 6		2033	1,900	80	120	130	660	2,890
7	Construction 1		2034	1,900	100	150	140	800	3,090
8	Construction 2		2035	2,000	150	150	150	800	3,250
9	Construction 3		2036	2,000	250	150	160	840	3,400
10	Construction 4		2037	2,100	350	200	170	840	3,660
11	Construction 5		2038	2,200	450	210	170	840	3,870
12	Construction 6		2039	2,300	550	260	180	1,150	4,440
13	Commssioning		2040	2,700	680	360	240	1,660	5,640
14	Operation 1	Z pole year 1	2041	3,200	800	500	400	2,200	7,100
15	Operation 2	Z pole year 2	2042	3,500	1,000	520	400	2,200	7,620
16	Operation 3	Z pole year 3	2043	3,800	1,100	500	400	2,200	8,000
17	Operation 4	Z pole year 4	2044	4,100	1,200	500	400	2,200	8,400
18	Operation 5	WW year 1	2045	4,300	1,300	540	400	2,200	8,740
19	Operation 6	WW year 2	2046	4,500	1,400	580	400	2,240	9,120
20	Operation 7	HZ year 1	2047	4,800	1,500	620	400	2,240	9,560
21	Operation 8	HZ year 2	2048	5,000	1,700	700	600	2,240	10,240
22	Operation 9	HZ year 3	2049	5,200	1,800	800	1,000	2,240	11,040
23	Operation 10	Upgrade	2050	5,100	1,800	850	1,400	2,400	11,550
24	Operation 11	Top year 1	2051	5,300	1,900	900	1,800	2,400	12,300
25	Operation 12	Top year 2	2052	5,500	2,100	900	1,800	2,400	12,700
26	Operation 13	Top year 3	2053	5,700	2,200	900	1,800	2,400	13,000
27	Operation 14	Top year 4	2054	5,700	2,300	900	1,800	2,400	13,100
28	Operation 15	Top year 5	2055	5,700	2,300	900	1,200	2,400	12,500
29	Post Operation 1	Analysis 1	2056	5,500	2,220	700	420	2,280	11,120
30	Post Operation 2	Analysis 2	2057	5,200	2,215	500	120	2,240	10,275
			Totals	106,500	31,720	13,710	16,450	47,920	216,300

Source: Authors.

Notes: Estimate of the sum of the persons that will engage in the scientific programme of the FCC, consisting of two experiments and a particle accelerator & technical infrastructure project.

7.2. REVIEW OF SOCIAL DISCOUNT RATES ADOPTED WORLDWIDE

Table 20. A review of SDRs adopted in selected countries worldwide.

Theoretical foundation	Country	Social Discount Rate (real)	Source
SRRI/SOC	Australia	7% with a sensitivity range from 3% to 10%	Australian Government (March 2020)
SRRI/SOC	Canada	8%, with sensitivity test over the range 3-10%	Treasury Board Secretary (2007) confirmed by Treasury Board Secretary (2020).
SRRI/SOC	Denmark	4% under 35 years (given by the sum of 3% risk-free rate and 1% risk premium). Reduced to 3% from 36 to 70 years and to 2% from year 71 onwards.	Mouter, N. (2018).
SRRI/SOC	India	12%	Campos, J et al (2015)
SRRI/SOC	Japan	4%	ITF (2015)
SRRI/SOC	Norway	4% under 40 years (given by the sum of 2.5% risk-free rate and 1.5% risk premium). Reduced to 3% from 40 to 75 years and to 2% from year 76 onwards.	NOU (2012)
SRRI/SOC	New Zealand	5% or 6% depending on the sector. (i) Default rate (for projects that are difficult to categorise including regulatory proposals, and most social sector projects): 5%; (ii) Office and Accommodation Buildings, Water, Energy, Hospitals, Hospital Energy Plans, Road and Other Transport projects: 5%; (iii) Telecommunications, Media and Technology, IT, R&D: 6%)	New Zealand Government (2015) New Zealand Government (2020)
SRRI/SOC	Pakistan	12%	Campos, J et al (2015)
SRRI/SOC	The Netherland	5.5% (2.5% real risk-free + 3% premium for macroeconomic risk) which can be reduced by up to 1.5% depending on project specific macroeconomic risk factor. The overall rate has been revised from 5.5% to 3% by the Netherlands Discount Rate Working Group in 2015. Also, different rates for specific policy areas are suggested (3% as a default rate or for investments in nature, CO ₂ and health; 4.5% for public physical investments/infrastructure and 5% for investments in education).	CPB and PBL (2013) Netherlands Discount Rate Working Group (2015) O'Callaghan et al. (2018)
SRRI/SOC	Philippines	10%	Moore, M. A. et al. (2020)
SRRI/SOC and SRTP	Latin American countries	Values from Government/agencies based on SRRI/SOC approach; Argentina: 12%; Bolivia: 12%; Chile: 6%; Colombia: 12%; Costa Rica: 12%; Mexico: 10%; Peru: 11%; Uruguay: 12%. Value calculated by Moore, M.A. et al on the basis of the SRTP approach: average SDR of 3.77%, ranging from 2.14% for Paraguay to 5.83% for Chile.	Moore, M. A. et al. (2020) ⁵¹
SRRI/SOC and SRTP	United States	7%, (SRRI) as a reference rate 3% (SRTP) to be applied in circumstance where the regulation primarily and directly affects private consumption OMB (2003) recommends lower rate for 'intergenerational' projects while US EPA (2013 and 2018) recommends 2.5% (SRTP) to account for the intergenerational nature of climate damages. DOE suggests a real discount rate of 3% for projects related to energy conservation, renewable energy resources, and water conservation.	OMB (2003) EPA 2013 and 2018 OECD, 2018 Cahill, N. and Dr O'Connell, L. (2018) U.S. Department of Commerce, National Institute of Standards and Technology (2013)
SRTP	European Union	5% is used in Cohesion countries and 3% for the other Member States	European Commission (2014)
SRTP	France	2.5% (falling to 1.5% from 2070) plus a risk premium of 2% (rising to 3% from 2070) multiplied by a sector specific beta value. When the macroeconomic sensitivity (β) of a project is not known, the Quinet Commission recommends the rate of 4.5%	Quinet (2013) and Ni, J. (2017).
SRTP	Germany	3% for short-term period (evaluations up to 20 years). 1.5% (constant) for cross-general evaluations (evaluations extending over 20 years) which should be combined with a sensitivity analysis using a discount rate of 0%.	German Federal Environment Agency (UBA, 2012).
SRTP	Ireland	a) 4% (for projects with long time horizons a declining discount rate applies) b) Range from 2.6% to 3.9% for all sectors. 1.7% for carbon emissions and other long-term environmental damage	a) Department of Public Expenditure and Reform (2019) and confirmed in January 2021 ⁵² b) Cahill, N. and Dr O'Connell, L. (2018)
SRTP	Italy	3%	Invitalia (2014)
SRTP	Malta	5.5%	Planning and Priorities Co-ordination Division (2013)
SRTP	Sweden	3.5%	ASEK Guidelines (2020)
SRTP	UK	3.5% for years 0-30, 3% years 31-75, 2.5% from year 76 onwards. For health projects: 1.50% for years 0-30; 1.29% years 31-75 and 1.07% % from year 76 onwards.	HM Treasury (2018) Freeman, M. et al (2018)
SRTP	Value recommended for an international governmental organization	The mean recommended SDR is 2.27%, with a range from 0 to 10%. More than three-quarters of experts are comfortable with the median SDR of 2%, and over 90% of respondents find an SDR in the range of 1 to 3% acceptable.	Drupp, M. A., et al (2015 and 2018)

⁵¹ Moore, M. A., et al 2020 provides a new estimation for the SDR basing on SRTP approach for the following countries: Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Ecuador, El Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras, Mexico, Nicaragua, Panama, Paraguay, Peru, Uruguay, Venezuela

⁵² <https://www.gov.ie/en/policy-information/1a0dcb-project-discount-inflation-rates/>

Source: Authors adapted from Catalano and Pancotti (2021).

7.3. ESTIMATED SALARY FUNCTIONS BY PROFESSIONAL SECTOR

Salary functions were calculated considering the following data and geographical and sector scope.

- Data were extracted from Glassdoor (www.glassdoor.com), a job-related website where registered users from all over the world can anonymously submit and view salaries as well as search and apply for jobs on the platform. Glassdoor data cover the majority of countries (European ones and the USA) in which people at CERN are likely to continue their careers after their experience at the laboratory (see below). A possible alternative to Glassdoor is the US salary database PayScale, which has been used in previous works dealing with the value of training benefit at CERN.⁵³ While being a valuable source of information, the PayScale database has the disadvantage of reporting only the salaries in the US labour market and therefore it does not cover the European labour market, which is the main destination of CERN researchers.
- The geographical and sector scope of the analysis was driven by the evidence shown by the CERN report by Bianchin et al. (2019). That report investigates the career trajectories of 2,692 people with working experience in the CERN experiments, which represents an extremely valuable sample of respondents and information to our purpose. For instance, the report shows that respondents work in more than 17 countries, but the large majority of them works in five countries: Switzerland (496 out of 2,692), the USA (416), Germany (299), Italy (247), and the UK (183). The remaining countries count less than 60 respondents.⁵⁴ Moreover, out of 1,937 participants who answered the multiple-answer question about the sector they work, 55% of respondents answered “academia”, followed by the private sector (ICT - 41%; financial institutions- 15%; high-tech companies - 15%), public administration (17%), and education in high school (13%). As regards the job titles of people who left CERN, most of them are employed as software engineer, followed by analyst, manager, and consultant.⁵⁵ We used these findings to drive our data collection strategy.

Glassdoor reports gross salary data (i.e. they include taxes) and are in national currencies. Salaries were expressed in Swiss francs (CHF) by using 2019 average bilateral exchange rates provided by the European Central Bank. The Team collected the data in May 2020 and assembled two databases with different pieces of information:

1. **The first database contains salary data at national level.** At that level, Glassdoor provides information on the average salary level by country and by job title, the minimum and maximum values. The website also informs about the reliability of data, through a 4-scale-point indicator (from very low to very high), which is linked to the number of records in that country. For instance, considering the job title “software engineer”, US salary records amount to 256,924 with a reliability “very high”; in the UK, they amount to 5,488, which is still “very high”; in Switzerland they were 386 with “high” reliability; in contrast, in Belgium there were only 30 records with a “low” reliability of salary data. **In total, the Team processed 812,000 records of salary data from 16 countries and 13 job titles.** Statistics at national level are reported in the Figure below. As mentioned above, the range of countries and job titles considered reflects the career profile of people with a working experience at CERN.
2. **The second database contains salary data at individual level.** Beyond salaries, the country, and the job title, Glassdoor users are asked to share the number of years of working experience, the sector and

⁵³ Florio et al. (2016) and Bastianin and Florio (2018). The first paper uses salary functions calculated on the US PayScale database to estimate the benefit associated with a period of training at the CERN Large Hadron Collider (LHC); the second one uses the same functions but applied to the Hi-Luminosity LHC. Throughout the document, comparisons between the salary functions obtained from the two sources data, i.e. PayScale and Glassdoor, are analysed to investigate on differences e/o similarities.

⁵⁴ Bianchin et al (2019), page 6, Figure 2.5.

⁵⁵ Bianchin et al (2019), page 15, Figure 2.18 and Figure 2.19.

the city where they work, and whether they receive any bonus in addition to the basic salary.⁵⁶ Personal information, and in particular the sector of employment and the years of working experience, can be only extracted for a limited number of records in a given country (the most recent records); therefore they are not available for the whole sample of records at national level. **In total, the Team collected 1 005 records covering 16 countries** (on average 63 per country) **and 13 job titles** (about 77 per job title).

The figure below (Panel A) compares the geographical distribution of salaries from the national database (with reliable average salaries, but no individual information) and the individual database (smaller number of records and therefore potentially less reliable average salaries by country, but more individual information). There are no significant differences between the two distributions, suggesting that individual data are reliable as well. Employees in Switzerland earn the highest gross salary (CHF 110 082 per year), followed by those in the USA (CHF 80 647), Germany (CHF 73 197), and Canada (CHF 63 855). The lowest salaries are paid in India. The average annual salary in the database amounts to about CHF 51 000.⁵⁷ Similarly, Panel B shows the distribution by job titles. **The two distributions are similar to each other, confirming the reliability of salary data from the individual database.**⁵⁸ As expected, directors register the highest salaries (CHF 100 000 per year), professors the second highest (about CHF 64 000 per year), while educators the lowest ones (about 33 000 per year).

Figure 13. Distribution of salaries: database at national level (CHF, annual)

PANEL A: Distribution by country of employment

PANEL B: Distribution by job title

⁵⁶ For each salary reported, Glassdoor removes the name of the company for privacy reasons, while showing the sector, years of experience and the presence of bonus or other benefits in addition to the salary.

⁵⁷ In addition, these data were also cross-checked with salaries reported in the Inomics Salary Report (2018). INOMICS is a platform which provides information on the career of students in Economics and offer students, professors, professionals and recruiters in the economics job market a comprehensive online resource for their academic and career choices since 1998. The 2018 report (page 21) states that “The highest salaries for almost all positions, both in academia and the private sector are earned in Switzerland, Canada and the United States. For instance, the highest salaries for PhD candidates are earned in Switzerland and Canada, with PhD candidates in Switzerland earning on average twice as much as those in Germany”.

⁵⁸ The job title “director” shows slightly higher salaries when individual data are considered because of outliers in the data (in the public administration sector). The Team removed them to simulate salaries functions.

Source: Authors' elaboration on Glassdoor data.

Note: The Figure shows the salary distribution by country and job title extracted from the Glassdoor national database. For each country and job title the mean (blue bar), the minimum (orange bar) and the maximum (green bar) are reported.

Figure 14. Distribution of salaries: national database vs. individual database (CHF, annual).

PANEL A: Distribution of salaries by country of employment

PANEL B: Distribution of salaries by job title

Source: Authors' elaboration on Glassdoor data.

The distributions of salaries by years of working experience and by sector are reported in Figure 15. Both are from the database at the individual level. People in the public administration sector report the highest salaries (CHF 61 162 per year), followed by employees in the industry e/o finance (CHF 53 271 per year) and finally academia or other research institutes (CHF 43 336 per year).

Figure 15. Distribution of salaries by years of experience and sector (CHF, annual).

Source: Authors' elaboration on Glassdoor data.

Figure 16 shows the salary functions obtained by (log-)interpolating the salary data with the years of working experience; while Table 5 in section 4.2.2 reports the formulas along with the parameters of the distributions of salaries by sector.⁵⁹ The Figure shows that the distribution of salaries has a positive skew, i.e. the mean is higher than the median, which is a stylised fact in the empirical salary distribution. Moreover, and as mentioned above, the salary functions and the other parameters are reported for the three sectors where the majority of CERN people are likely to be employed: academia and research, industry/finance, and public administration. In addition, a fourth salary function grouping all the three sectors above and labelled “All sectors” is showed, which can be applied as reference for the salary trajectory for those people for which the information about the sector of employed is lacking/or cannot be predicted.

Figure 16. Salary functions developed for the FCC-ee socio-economic impact analysis.

⁵⁹ Mincer (1974) modelled the natural logarithm of earnings as a function of years of education and years of (potential) labour market experience (age minus year of schooling minus six). The Mincer equation stems from the Ben Porath's lifecycle model “Human Capital Investment over the Lifecycle” (Ben Porath, 1967). Glassdoor data do not have information on the number of years of education of users. Interpolating salary data with years of experience is the best one can do with those data.

Source: Authors' elaboration on Glassdoor data.

Note: Elaborations are net of outliers: 7 observations (out of 222) in the Public administration sector were removed. Such observations were “directors” earning more than CHF 200,000 per year. The R^2 gives an indication of the goodness of the interpolation and ranges from 0 (the worst fit) to 1 (the best fit). It is as follows: Academia_ Research ($R^2=0.93$); Industry/Finance ($R^2=0.78$); Public administration ($R^2=0.83$); All sectors ($R^2=0.89$).

While valuable, Glassdoor data have some limitations. For instance, they do not report the education level of users, which is extremely important to explain the variability across individual salaries (years of experience only tells us part of the story) (Mincer, 1974). Moreover, primary data are needed to estimate more accurate salary functions (Psacharopoulos and Patrinos, 2018; Lemieux, 2006; Mincer, 1974). For that reason, the Team and the CERN have launched in April 2020 a detailed survey to people with a working experience at CERN in order to collect, among other, fresh information on job-related variables, including salaries. At the time of writing, the survey is still on-going, and therefore results will be discussed in due course.

7.4. ESTIMATED DURATION OF ACTIVE WORKING LIFE

Bianchini et al. (2019) report on a recent survey conducted by the CERN Alumni initiative aimed at studying the career trajectories of people with a working experience at CERN (on experiments). 2 692 responses were collected from both current and past members of LHC and other CERN experiments. More than 85% of people hold a PhD and are experimental physicists, a share that is also confirmed by other studies.⁶⁰ Moreover, Fig. 2.18 on page 15 in the Bianchini et al. (2019)'s study shows that the variety of sectors in which CERN people are likely to continue their careers after their experience at CERN is broad. Out of 1 937 participants who answered the multiple-answer question about the sector they work, 55% of respondents answered “academia”, followed by the information technology in the private sector (41%), government sector (17%), financial institutions (15%), high-tech companies (14%), and education in high school (13%). Therefore, people at CERN

⁶⁰ Camporesi et al (2017).

show higher educational levels (doctoral degree) and mainly continue their professional career in education (academia and high school) and to a lower extent in the private industry and service sectors.

According to Eurostat, **the average expected duration of working life in the EU28 in 2019 was 36.4 years.** The gap between men and women is 4.8 years, with men at 38.6 years, and women at 33.8 years. The expected average duration among the EU Member States ranges from 32 years in Italy to 42 years in Sweden (Table 21, Column 1).⁶¹ This is in line with OECD (2020) figures as well. According to these figures, we have that on average:

- A person who has entered the labor market at the age of 15 is likely to retire at 52 years;
- A person who has entered the labor market at the age of 20 is likely to retire at 57 years;
- A person who has entered the labor market at the age of 30 is likely to retire at 67 years.

Retirement from paid work at the age of 65, and often earlier, has been the norm in the EU until recent years (Eurofound, 2020). Indeed, the normal retirement age in Europe, i.e. the age at which an individual can retire without any reduction to her/his pension, is about 65 (Column 2, Table 21 and blue lines in Figure 17) and the same is true for the OECD countries (64.2 for men and 63.5 for women) (OECD, 2019a).⁶² Moreover, there is no significant difference between the normal retirement age and the effective one. For instance, in the OECD countries the effective retirement age is 65.4 for men and 63.7 for women. There are no significant differences in the retirement ages between sectors as well. Apart from non-standard workers for whom specific pension rules are currently in force⁶³ and ad-hoc pension schemes for workers in arduous and hazardous jobs,⁶⁴ the normal retirement age has been 65 in the majority of EU countries in all sectors. For example, Column 3 in Table 21 reports the effective retirement age of the academic staff in the EU. It typically ranges from 65 to 67 years, with some exceptions to 70 years. There are no differences in terms of pensions legislation between the education sector and other sectors of the economy.⁶⁵

While the retirement at age of 65 and earlier has been the norm until now, **the age at which people retire has been rising.** According to Eurofound (2020), as the ‘baby boom’ generation moves into retirement, more workers will be retiring than those entering the labour market. With an increasing life expectancy and birth rates falling across Europe, a priority of EU policy is to encourage Europeans to extend their active work life to ensure the sustainability of pension systems and adequate social protection. Many older workers are also increasingly wishing to continue working. Eurostat data show that in general and for all the sectors, the average length of working life in the EU28 is increasing over time. In 2019, it was 0.5 years longer than in 2018 and 3.5 years longer than in 2000.⁶⁶ Changes in retirement ages are scheduled to take place between 2020 and 2030 in most of the EU countries. Column 4 in Table 21 (orange lines in Figure 17) reports the future retirement age as scheduled by the EU Member States.⁶⁷ In the next future, the compulsory retirement age will be in the range of 67-70 years in many EU countries, with an expected duration of working life going from 39 to 42 years and even more in some countries such as Sweden, Netherlands, and Estonia

⁶¹European Commission (2020). Duration of working life -statistics. Available here: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/pdfscache/57155.pdf>. Last access on 25.05.2020. The discussion in the text above does not take into account the European Candidate Countries (Montenegro; North Macedonia, Albania, Serbia, Turkey) and EFTA Countries (Iceland, and Norway).

⁶² Estimates derived from the European and national labour force surveys. See OECD (2019a).

⁶³ They are workers not covered by fulltime open-ended contracts, i.e. part-time, temporary or self-employed workers for whom specific pension rules are currently in force, even if efforts have been implementing on how to make pension systems more inclusive given transforming labour markets. (OECD, 2019a).

⁶⁴ Although there has been a debate on what are the “hard job” categories and the “generosity of pensions for workers in “hard jobs”, in some rare cases, countries pushed through reforms creating more favourable conditions for these categories. For instance, Finland set up a new scheme for workers in arduous and hazardous jobs: the “years-of-services pension” (minimum pensionable age of 63). France established a “personal prevention account” which allow workers to acquire points as a result of exposure to six risk factors; while Italy has introduced special rules for workers in arduous and hazardous jobs, allowing them to retire prior to reaching the pensionable age, under certain conditions. On-going policy discussion along these lines are currently taking place in Belgium, Croatia, and Slovakia. See Cabral and Rodrigues (2019).

⁶⁵ See for instance the European Commission’s Eurydice platform, which shares information and data on the European education systems updated to April 2020).

⁶⁶ In 2000, the average length of working life in the EU28 was 32.9 years. European Commission (2020; p.4).

⁶⁷ See Finnish Centre for Pensions (2020) and Eurofound (2020).

In the light of this evidence and to estimate the impact of “value of training” of the future FCC project, **it is recommended to set the total average active working life for researchers and scientists working at CERN to a range between 39 and 42 years.** Let us consider the following example: if no work experience exists before entering in a PhD programme, students are on average between 26-28 years old when they first enter a doctoral programme (OECD, 2019b; p. 345).⁶⁸ Considering that the average duration of a full-time doctoral program is 3-4 years,⁶⁹ this means that PhDs enter the labour market at an age around 29-32. When working for at least 39 years they would retire at an age between 68 and 71 years.

The range 39 and 42 years is in line with the observed trend of increasing work duration and future pension plans across all the major developed countries and sectors, including academia. It is also aligned with the career duration assumed for the LHC and HL-LHC socio-economic impact assessment, which was 42 years⁷⁰ and with the literature on human capital, which often sets the maximum years of potential working experience at 40.⁷¹ This range is slightly lower than the duration of working life assumed in a recent OECD study which sets it, on average, at 44 years.⁷²

Table 21. Duration of working life and retirement age in EU member States and some extra-EU country

Country/ Area	Column 1			Column 2	Column 3	Column 4
	Duration of working life (all sectors)			Current (2020) normal retirement age in all sectors (years)	Effective retirement age of academic staff (years)	Future normal retirement age (years)
	Total	Male	Female	Male/Female		
EU 27	35.9	38.3	33.4			
EU 28	36.4	38.7	33.9			
Belgium	33.6	35.4	31.6	65	65	67 (by 2030)
Bulgaria	34.0	35.6	32.3	66.5	65	67 (by 2023)
Czechia	36.3	39.2	33.2	63.7	63-65	65 (by 2036)
Denmark	40.0	41.7	38.2	67/66	65-70	68+ (by 2030)
Germany	39.1	41.1	36.9	65.7		67 (by 2031)
Estonia	39.0	39.5	38.5	63.7		68+ (by 2027)
Ireland	37.4	40.7	33.9	66	65-70	68 (by 2028)
Greece	33.2	36.6	29.6	67	67	67+ (by 2021)
Spain	35.3	37.4	33.1	65.8	65-70	67 (by 2027)
France	35.4	37.0	33.8	66.5	65-67	67 (by 2023)
Croatia	32.5	34.5	30.5	65/62.5	65	67 (by 2038)
Italy	32.0	36.4	27.3	67	65-70	67+ (by 2022)
Cyprus	37.5	40.5	34.4	65	67	65+ (by 2023)
Latvia	36.8	36.8	36.8	63.8	65	65 (by 2025)
Lithuania	37.1	36.7	37.5	64/63	65	65 (by 2026)
Luxembourg	33.9	36.0	31.6	65		
Hungary	34.4	37.4	31.2	64.5	65	65 (by 2022)
Malta	36.5	41.1	31.8	63	62-67	65 (by 2027)
Netherlands	41.0	43.3	38.6	64.3	66-67	67+ (by 2022)
Austria	37.6	39.8	35.3	65/60	65	65 (by 2033)
Poland	33.6	36.3	30.7	65/60	65	
Portugal	38.2	39.6	36.8	66.5	70	
Romania	33.8	37.0	30.3	65/61.5		
Slovenia	35.9	37.0	34.7	65	65	
Slovakia	34.2	36.6	31.6	62.5	70	63+ (by 2024)
Finland	38.9	39.6	38.3	68/65	65	65+ (by 2030)
Sweden	42.0	42.9	41.0	62-68/65	65-67	66+ (by 2026)

⁶⁸ It depends on the age at which students graduate from a lower level of higher education and the flexibility of the national education system (OECD, 2019b).

⁶⁹ Several European universities websites have been revised.

⁷⁰ Bastianin and Florio (2018); Florio et al (2016).

⁷¹ Psacharopoulos, G. and Patrinos, H.A. (2018); Lemieux, T. (2006)

⁷² The OECD (2019a; Table 5.2) reports cases of people entering in the labour market in 2018 at age 22 (birth cohort 1996). Although the pension age differs among countries because of national scheduled pension plans, on average, it is estimated that such people would retire at an age of 66, i.e. 44 years of active working life.

UK	39.4	41.5	37.2	65 o 66	65	68 (by 2046)
Iceland	45.8	47.8	43.7	67		
Norway	39.8	41.1	38.4	62-75/67		
Switzerland	42.6	44.6	40.4	65/64	64-65	
Montenegro	32.7	36.0	29.2		67	
N. Macedonia	31.7	36.8	26.4			
Serbia	33.4	36.4	30.2		65-68	
Turkey	29.3	39.0	19.1		65-67	
Australia				58/66		65 (by 2025)/ 67 (by 2023)
Canada				65		
Japan				65		
Russia				60.5/55.5		65 (by 2028)/60 (by 2028)
USA				66		67 (by 2027)

Source: Column 1, Duration of working life: Eurostat. Variable [lfsi_dwl_a]. Raw data are available here:

https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=lfsi_dwl_a&lang=en .

Columns 2 and 4: Finnish Centre for Pensions, <https://www.etk.fi/en/the-pension-system/international-comparison/retirement-ages/>

Column 3: European Commission's Eurydice platform. https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/eurydice/home_en Search for "Conditions of Service for Academic Staff Working in Higher Education")

Figure 17. Current and future duration of working life in EU member states.

Source: Authors' elaboration on data in Table 21.

Note: Ad-hoc pension schemes for workers in arduous and hazardous jobs are excluded.

Considering that

- retirement from paid work at the age of 65, and often earlier, has been the norm in the EU until recent years and that, in line with that norm, the average expected duration of working life in the EU28 was 36.4 years in 2019 (Eurostat),
- no systematic differences exist in terms of normal retirement age between sectors, including academia (with the exception of non-standard workers and risky jobs) (European Commission, OECD),
- in the future, the compulsory retirement age will increase in many European countries to a range of 67-70 years (Eurofound, OECD) and as a result, the expected duration of working life will increase up to 39 - 42 years (OECD),

we set the total average active working life for researchers and scientists working at FCC-ee between 39 and 42 years. This also fits with the characteristics of people who have had a working experience at CERN, i.e. with the fact that 85% of them have a PhD (Bianchin et al., 2019) and PhDs enter into the labour market at an age between 29 and 32 and are likely to leave between 67-70 (especially if they work in academia).

Figure 18 shows **the probability distribution of the total active working life with probabilities associated to three periods: 39 years, 40 years, 41-42 years.** Probabilities are calculated as the ratio between the number of countries with that total active working life out of the total number of countries ($N = 29$, including EU28 and USA).⁷³

⁷³ It is important to include the USA because it represents the second country after Switzerland where people go to work after their experiential learning at CERN. For instance, the study by Bianchin et al. (2019) shows that out of 2,692 trained people at CERN who participated to the survey on career trajectories, 496 people work and reside in Switzerland, 416 in the US, 299 in Germany, 427 in Italy, and 2115 in France (Bianchin et al. 2019; Figure 2.5).

Figure 18. Probability distribution of the total active working life.

Source: Authors' elaboration on data in Table 21.

Note: The period 39 years includes 19 countries out of 29. They have a future normal retirement age of maximum 39 years and are: CY, IE, LT, LV, MT, CZ, SI, FR, ES, HU, SK, BG, LU, RO, BE, PL, EL, HR, IT. The period 40 years includes 5 countries out of 29. They are: DE, AT, USA, FI, and PT (assumption). The period 41-42 years includes 5 countries out of 29. They have a future normal retirement age of minimum 41 years and are: UK, EE, DK, NL, SE.

7.5. WILLINGNESS-TO-PAY VALUES FOR NON-USERS OF THE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Table 22. Determinants of the WTP (secondary source data - 2019).

Country	Per-capita GDP (EUR)	Per-capita GDP (CHF)	% of People with tertiary education	% of people aged less than 35	% of people with a family size more than 3 members	% of people employed in Science and Technology (S&T)	% of scientists and engineers	Avg. science literacy scores of 15-year-old students (min 0; max 1000)
CERN Member States								
Austria	44,780	49,706	29.8	24.6	17.5	24.4	6.0	490
Belgium	41,460	46,021	34.5	24.3	19.3	22.4	6.0	499
Bulgaria	8,780	9,746	23.7	21.7	21.8	15.6	3.9	424
Czechia	20,990	23,299	20.1	22.2	20.1	21.6	4.5	497
Denmark	53,760	59,674	31.3	25.4	13.1	30.1	7.2	493
Finland	43,570	48,363	37.3	24.0	12.7	28.5	7.4	522
France	35,960	39,916	31.8	23.5	18.0*	22.0	4.0	493
Germany	41,510	46,076	25.8	23.1	12.7	28.1	5.4	503
Greece	17,100	18,981	25.9	21.2	25.1	13.4	3.3	452
Hungary	14,950	16,595	21.9	23.4	18.5	19.0	3.9	481
Italy	29,660	32,923	16.5	20.7	20.1*	17.0	2.6	468
Netherlands	46,710	51,848	32.5	25.1	17.2	29.9	7.4	503
Norway	67,370	74,781	36.6	26.2	14.0	29.5	8.1	490
Poland	13,870	15,396	26.2	24.9	29.5	20.0	4.7	511
Portugal	20,740	23,021	21.6	21.6	19.6	19.1	5.5	492
Romania	11,530	12,798	14.8	23.4	26.9	12.8	3.8	426
Slovakia	17,210	19,103	22.0	25.1	33.7*	17.7	2.8	464
Spain	26,430	29,337	32.4	21.2	23.1	16.6	4.2	483
Sweden	46,130	51,204	36.6	25.3	14.2	32.9	8.7	499
Switzerland	76,200	84,582	37.1	24.4	17.8*	31.6	9.6	495
United Kingdom	37,750	41,903	36.8	25.3	19.3*	26.1	7.7	505
Associate Member States in the pre-stage to Membership								
Cyprus	25,310	28,094	37.4	29.7	27.9	19.9	4.5	439
Serbia	6,620	7,348	20.2	23.3	32.8	13.6	2.7	440
Slovenia	23,170	25,719	27.5	21.5	23.8	22.4	5.3	507
Associate Member States								
Lithuania	17,460	19,381	36.1	23.8	16.6	21.9	5.4	482
Turkey	8,230	9,135	17.5	31.2	43.4*	8.3	1.7	468

Source: All the variables are from Eurostat and refers to 2019. * 2018 data (2019 not available). Percentages are calculated as share of the population aged between 15 and 74. Science literacy is from OECD Program for International Student Assessment (PISA). Scores are reported on a scale from 0 to 1,000.